

Tree-based Solutions
4 Climate Change **Adaptation**
& Biodiversity Conservation

D5.1 - Plan for the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication of results (PDEC)

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Table of Contents

1.	Abbreviations	5
2.	Executive summary	6
3.	Introduction	6
3.1.	Rationale	7
3.2.	Objectives	7
4.	Key Principles Guiding the PDEC	7
4.1.	Definitions and terminology	7
4.2.	Rights, rules and obligations related to results	8
4.2.1.	Ownership of results	8
4.2.2.	Protection of results	9
4.2.3.	Exploitation of results	9
	Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) & Management	9
4.2.4.	Communication and dissemination of results	10
	Open Science and Open Access (OA) to scientific publications	10
4.2.5.	Visibility of funding	13
4.3.	General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) implications	14
4.3.1.	GDPR compliance (website, mailing list and events)	14
5.	Pre- and Post-Dissemination Requirements	15
5.1.	Pre-dissemination requirements	15
5.1.1.	When These Procedures Apply	15
5.1.2.	Prior Notice Procedure	15
5.1.3.	Intellectual Property (IP) Assessment	17
5.1.4.	Scientific Publication Guidelines	19
5.2.	Post-dissemination requirements	22
5.2.1.	Continuous Reporting of Scientific Publications	22
5.2.2.	Continuous Reporting of Dissemination and Communication Activities	22
5.2.3.	Patents (IPR) reporting	23
5.2.4.	Datasets	24
5.2.5.	Overview of Post-Dissemination Continuous Reporting Protocols	24
6.	Stakeholder engagement	24
6.1.	Internal stakeholders - project bodies	25
6.1.1.	The General Assembly (GeA)	25
6.1.2.	The Executive Board (EB)	26
6.1.3.	The Stakeholder Board (SB)	27
6.1.4.	The Case Study (CS) leaders	27
6.2.	Stakeholder engagement strategy	28
6.2.1.	STIR approach	28
6.2.2.	Prospex-CQI method	29
6.3.	Trees4Adapt-specific stakeholder activities	30
6.3.1.	Local-level engagement	30
	Insights from case study engagement	31

6.3.2.	Regional, national and EU-level engagement	33
6.3.3.	EU-level legacy event	34
7.	Management of results and exploitation	34
7.1.	Expected end-user groups, pathways and impact	34
❖	Industry and practice	37
❖	Public authorities, policymakers, and regulators	37
❖	Scientific community	37
❖	Civil society, NGOs, communities	37
❖	Related EU projects, initiatives	37
❖	Trees4Adapt stakeholder network	38
7.2.	Exploitation management approach	42
7.2.1.	Output identification and collection.....	42
7.2.2.	Co-creation, testing, and refinement of outputs.....	42
7.2.3.	Roles and responsibilities	43
8.	Dissemination and communication resources and activities.....	44
8.1.	Promotional materials.....	44
8.1.1.	Logo and brand.....	44
8.1.2.	Project dissemination templates.....	45
8.1.3.	Factsheet.....	45
8.1.4.	Infographics	46
8.1.5.	Website.....	46
8.1.6.	Social media	48
8.1.7.	Project videos	50
8.1.8.	Press releases and promotional articles.....	50
8.1.9.	Other resources and tools.....	51
8.2.	Activities	51
8.2.1.	PDEC tools, channels and audiences	51
8.2.2.	External events	54
8.2.3.	Scientific publications – relevant journals.....	55
9.	PDEC monitoring and evaluation.....	56
10.	Project participants involved in the work.....	56
11.	Appendix	57
➤	Annexe 1 – IP Assessment Evaluation Page.....	57
➤	Annexe 2 – Trees4Adapt continuous reporting logs	58

1. Abbreviations

<i>CA</i>	Consortium Agreement
<i>CS</i>	Case study
<i>D</i>	Deliverable
<i>DEC</i>	Dissemination, exploitation, and communication
<i>DMP</i>	Data management plan
<i>EB</i>	Executive Board
<i>EC</i>	European Commission
<i>EU</i>	European Union
<i>FAIR</i>	Findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable
<i>GA</i>	Grant Agreement
<i>GeA</i>	General Assembly
<i>GDPR</i>	General Data Protection Regulation
<i>IP</i>	Intellectual property
<i>IPR</i>	Intellectual property right
<i>KER</i>	Key Exploitable Result
<i>M#</i>	Month #
<i>NbS</i>	Nature-based solutions
<i>NGOs</i>	Non-governmental organisations
<i>OA</i>	Open access
<i>PDEC</i>	Plan for the dissemination, exploitation, and communication
<i>SB</i>	Stakeholder Board
<i>STIR</i>	Stakeholder Integrated Research
<i>TbS</i>	Tree-based solutions
<i>WP</i>	Work package

2. Executive summary

The Trees4Adapt Plan for the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication of results (PDEC) – D5.1, brings together all processes, tools, and responsibilities related to stakeholder engagement, dissemination, exploitation, and communication across the consortium. It describes how key project knowledge is managed and shared, how intellectual property is safeguarded, and how the consortium ensures that key results reach scientific, policy, and practitioner audiences. The PDEC outlines the internal procedures for coordinating communication activities, identifying and engaging stakeholder groups, supporting the uptake and exploitation of project outputs, and ensuring compliance with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement (GA) and the European Commission's (EC) guidance on Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC). The PDEC summarises briefly the stakeholder engagements and DEC activities that have already taken place. As a living document, it is updated at project reporting milestones (Month 18, Month 36 and Month 48) to reflect progress, refine practices, and capture lessons learned throughout the project.

3. Introduction

The overall goal of **Trees4Adapt (Addressing complex risks from climate change and biodiversity loss across systems and scales: Leveraging the potential of tree-based solutions for adaptation in Europe)** is to strengthen Europe's ability to understand, assess, and respond to the interconnected challenges of climate change and biodiversity loss. These dual crises create complex, multi-scale risks that can only be addressed through integrated knowledge and decision-support tools, as well as practical solutions co-developed with the stakeholders who will use them. **Trees4Adapt** will achieve this by: **1)** improving empirical understanding of climate change, biodiversity loss, and their interdependencies across boreal, temperate, and Mediterranean biomes; **2)** developing high-resolution modelling and risk assessment tools that combine ecological, climatic, and socio-economic information; **3)** co-creating, testing, and evaluating tree-based solutions (TbS) that are stakeholder-validated and enhance climate resilience while supporting biodiversity; **4)** producing policy recommendations and practical guidance on the extent to which TbS address complex risks from climate change and biodiversity loss, tailored to the needs of public authorities, land managers, farmers, and other relevant actors; **5)** integrating findings across scales through interdisciplinary research platforms; and **6)** disseminating and communicating project results to promote their uptake among scientific, policy, and practitioner communities.

Active engagement with key societal stakeholders is central to **Trees4Adapt's** approach. Public administrations, forest and land managers, farmers, policymakers, the scientific community, and other actors will guide the project's research through co-creation activities, bilateral consultations, and iterative validation processes. To ensure the relevance, adoption, and long-term impact of the project's outputs, **Trees4Adapt** consolidates stakeholder engagement, dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities within a single Work Package (*WP5 – Stakeholder engagement, dissemination, exploitation & communication*). WP5 coordinates the co-creation processes in the case studies, stakeholder mapping and engagement at all governance levels, targeted communication and outreach, collaboration with related EU initiatives, and the development of a post-project exploitation strategy.

All project partners are actively involved in these activities to maximise the project's impact and legacy.

3.1. Rationale

The **Trees4Adapt** PDEC outlines the DEC strategies to be implemented by the consortium throughout the project lifetime and beyond.

Adopting the EC's best practice guidelines and aligning with rights and obligations outlined in the **Trees4Adapt** Grant Agreement (GA) related to dissemination and exploitation, the PDEC describes internal processes and protocols set up to support communication, manage generated knowledge and ensure exploitation of **Trees4Adapt's** results. It identifies key project stakeholders, communication tools and channels and describes the means of dissemination and measures to support exploitation.

3.2. Objectives

The PDEC aims to:

- Provide a useful guide to all members of the **Trees4Adapt** consortium about rules and responsibilities surrounding DEC.
- Promote the project activities and results beyond the consortium by employing a range of communication and dissemination tools.
- Identify and profile the **target stakeholders** for the different key project results (also called Key Exploitable Results – KERs, [see PDEC section 7.1](#)).
- Define the most effective dissemination and exploitation channels, tools, and means, tailored to the relevant stakeholders.
- Outline **exploitation** guidelines to ensure the effective dissemination of **KERs** to **targeted groups**, maximising both short- and long-term **impact** and post-project uptake, while safeguarding **intellectual property (IP)**.

The **Trees4Adapt PDEC** is regularly updated to describe and inform partners of the **stakeholder engagement** and **DEC activities** performed and planned to ensure the exploitation of the project's outputs, its maximum impact and the availability of the gained knowledge for all interested organisations. It is a dynamic document and will be evaluated and updated at EC reporting stages (D5.5: M18 - March 2027 and D5.7: M36 - Sep 2028), and at the project's end (D5.11: M48 - Sep 2029), allowing for adjustments as needed.

4. Key Principles Guiding the PDEC

4.1. Definitions and terminology

The foundation of the **Trees4Adapt PDEC** is a coordinated approach to managing and sharing project results from the start of the project, ensuring that communication, dissemination, and

exploitation activities are coherently planned and implemented in line with the European Commission (EC) definitions¹, as follows:

- **Communication** is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the project and continues throughout its entire lifetime. It is aimed at promoting **Trees4Adapt** and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about **Trees4Adapt** and the project's results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. Activities used for communication purposes are, e.g., a public website, press releases, news articles or social media posts.
- **Dissemination** is the public disclosure of the project results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific [or professional] publication in any medium. It makes research results known to various stakeholder groups in a targeted way, enabling them to use the results in their own work. Activities used for dissemination purposes are, e.g., conferences, education and training events, publication in scientific journals, clustering activities and collaboration with other EU-funded projects.
- **Exploitation of results** is more advanced than communication and dissemination; it involves the use of results in further [innovation and deployment] activities other than those covered by the project, including, among other things, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities. It requires several steps, including identifying exploitation mechanisms and activities, focused on **identified end users to ensure impact and uptake of the results**, which will provide measurable impacts for **Trees4Adapt**, while ensuring any project-generated IP is properly managed.

4.2. Rights, rules and obligations related to results

This section outlines a summary of some key aspects of the rights and obligations relating to the protection of these results; however, it is not an exhaustive summary. For further details on the project and Horizon Europe rules surrounding ownership and protection of results, please refer to the Grant Agreement (GA), Consortium Agreement (CA), and please see **D6.2 Preliminary Data Management Plan** (DMP; due in M6 - March 2026) for specific rules for data outputs.

4.2.1. Ownership of results

Results are owned by the participant who generates them.

Two or more project participants' own results jointly if they have jointly generated them and it is not possible to establish the respective contribution of each participant, or separate them,

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/support/reference_terms.html;
https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/temp-form/report/periodic-report-horizon-euratom_en.pdf

for the purpose of applying for, obtaining, or maintaining their protection (GA Article 16 – Annexe 5; CA section 8).

Unless otherwise agreed, each joint owner is entitled to grant non-exclusive licences to third parties and to use/exploit jointly owned results (without any right to sub-license), if the other joint owners are given (i) at least 45 days' advance notice and (ii) fair and reasonable compensation (CA section 8.2).

Joint owners must agree, in advance and in writing, on the allocation and terms of exercise of their joint ownership (joint ownership agreement), all protection measures, the division of related cost in advance and ensure that rights to the results (including cases where they are claimed by third parties) can be exercised in a manner compatible with its obligations under the Agreement (GA Article 16 – Annexe 5; CA Section 8).

The beneficiaries must indicate the owner(s) of the results (results ownership list) in the final periodic report.

4.2.2. Protection of results

Each participant has an obligation to protect their results. Project participants who have received funding under the grant must adequately protect their results [for an appropriate period and with appropriate territorial coverage] if protection is possible and justified, taking into account all relevant considerations, including the prospects for commercial exploitation, the legitimate interests of the other project participants and any other legitimate interests (GA Article 16 – Annexe 5).

4.2.3. Exploitation of results

Each participant has an obligation to exploit their results. Project participants who have received funding under the grant must, up to four years after the end of the action, use their best efforts to exploit their results directly or to have them exploited indirectly by another entity, through transfer or licensing.

If, despite a participant's best efforts, the results are not exploited within one year after the end of the action, the project participants must (unless otherwise agreed in writing with the granting authority) use the Horizon Results Platform to find interested parties to exploit the results (see GA Article 16 – Annexe 5 for further details).

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) & Management

Trees4Adapt will follow the rules for IP set out and regulated by the EC. More information can be found in GA (Article 16.4) "Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) - Background and Results - Access Rights and Rights of Use", GA (Annexe 5), and CA section 9 (attachment 1).

The **Trees4Adapt's Executive Board**, composed of the Coordinators, Administrative Manager, WP Leaders and other members appointed by the General Assembly, will support IPR protection through assessing results, including their exploitation potential, as part of the knowledge management and transfer process. The project participants will ensure that adequate steps towards protection are taken prior to DEC, preventing unapproved public

disclosure of results, tools, products and services. Participants are asked to record information about potential IP before dissemination activities involving new results, by filling out the **Trees4Adapt Prior Notice Form** ([see PDEC section 5.1](#)). The information recorded will be double-checked by the project coordinator (Luke) and, when necessary, the EB to ensure protection of results.

4.2.4. Communication and dissemination of results

Each participant must disseminate their results as soon as possible by disclosing them to the public. However, no dissemination may take place before a decision is made regarding possible protection ([see PDEC section 5.1](#)). Other participants may object if their legitimate interests in relation to their results or background could potentially suffer harm. Results that are disclosed too early (before the decision on their protection) may run the risk of making protection impossible.

Therefore, project participants who intend to disseminate their results must give at least 30 calendar days' prior notice ([see PDEC section 5.1.2](#)) **to other project participants**, together with sufficient information on the results they intend to disseminate (CA section 8.4).

Any other participant may **object within** (unless agreed otherwise) **15 calendar days of receiving notification** if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests.

NO dissemination at all may take place if:

- the results in question need to be protected as a trade secret (i.e. confidential know-how) or
- dissemination conflicts with any other obligations under the GA (e.g. personal data protection, security obligations, etc).

Open Science and Open Access (OA) to scientific publications

'Open Science' is an approach based on open cooperative work and systematic sharing of knowledge and tools as early and widely as possible in the research process.

The open science provisions in Horizon Europe contain a set of requirements and encouraged practices that cover some of the most important aspects of open science. They concern research outputs such as scientific publications and research data, and additional open science practices.

'Research outputs' are results to which online access can be given in the form of scientific publications, data or other engineered outcomes and processes, such as software, algorithms, protocols, models, workflows and electronic notebooks.

This section outlines OA requirements for scientific publications. For more information on open science in relation to research data management and FAIR principles, please see the **Trees4Adapt DMP** (D6.2 due in M6 - March 2026) and the [Trees4Adapt Project Manual](#) (D6.1 delivered in M3 - Dec 2025).

Providing OA to peer-reviewed scientific publications in Horizon Europe-funded projects is an obligation for all grants (GA Article 17 – Annexe 5).

Beneficiaries must ensure OA to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results. This includes articles and long-text formats, such as monographs and other types of books. Doctoral theses may follow institutional embargo periods, provided that peer-reviewed publications derived from the thesis comply with Horizon Europe's immediate OA requirements, i.e., at the same time as the first publication, through a trusted repository using specific open licences.

How to provide OA (source: Annotated GA HE):

Beneficiaries/authors may publish in the venue of their choice, either in a closed venue (i.e. access to all content is restricted), an OA publishing venue or in a hybrid publishing venue, provided that all their OA-related obligations as detailed in the GA are complied with. Note that OA can also be ensured by depositing an accepted author copy on a DOI-indexed repository.

'OA publishing venues' are publishing venues whose entire scholarly content is published in OA (e.g. *open access journals, books, publishing platforms, repositories or preprint servers*).

'Hybrid publishing venues' are publishing venues which provide part of their scholarly content in OA, while another part is accessible through subscriptions/payments (e.g. *hybrid journals and books*). These are often journals/books based on subscription/purchase, which provide OA to part of their content when an OA fee is paid by their authors/institutions (paid ad hoc or on the basis of an institutional agreement with the publishers).

'Mirror and sister journals' (i.e. more recently established OA versions of existing subscription journals, which may share the same editorial board as the original journal and usually have (at least initially) the same or very similar aims, scope and peer review processes and policies; these journals often have a name similar to the subscription title (but a different ISSN) are considered OA publishing venues for HE grants (not hybrid journals).

In parallel, beneficiaries/authors must deposit their publication in a machine-readable format in a trusted repository before or at the time of publication and make it openly accessible through that repository. For Trees4Adapt, the trusted repository is the [Trees4Adapt Zenodo community](#), see **Trees4Adapt DMP** (D6.2 due in M6 - March 2026). Authors must deposit the author-accepted manuscript (or published version, when permitted) in the **Trees4Adapt Zenodo community**, even if the article is already openly accessible on the publisher's website.

 Publishing in an **open access venue** without depositing in a repository, does NOT comply with the open access requirements. All peer-reviewed publications must be deposited in trusted repositories and open access provided to them through the repositories.

Best practice: Beneficiaries are encouraged to provide OA to ALL publications, even if they are not peer-reviewed.

When choosing the publishing venue and the repository, beneficiaries/authors must keep in mind that licensing requirements, metadata requirements and validation requirements must also be complied with at this time.

⚠ The European Commission offers Horizon Europe beneficiaries [Open Research Europe \(ORE\)](#), an **open access publishing platform with no publishing fees**. ORE is offered as an additional publishing option to Horizon Europe beneficiaries. When ORE is the selected publishing venue, all requirements for open access to scientific publications are automatically fulfilled, as ORE deposits publications in the all-purpose repository [Zenodo under the conditions required by Horizon Europe](#).

Immediate OA through the repository must be provided either to the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication or to the final published peer-reviewed version.

Please also note that **publication fees are only eligible when publishing in full OA publishing venues (venues in which the entire scholarly content is openly accessible to all) and not in hybrid venues**. Publication fees may, in particular, include peer review fees, including where the peer review service has been provided by an organisation different from the one providing the publishing venue. Peer review fees for publications are eligible for reimbursement only for the first round of peer reviewers.

⚠ **Publishing fees** (including page charges or colour charges) for publications in other venues, for example in subscription journals (including hybrid journals) or in books that contain some scholarly content that is open and some that is closed are NOT eligible costs.

⚠ **Publishing fees** for open access books may be eligible to the extent that they cover the first digital open access edition of the book (which could include different formats such as html, pdf, epub, etc.).

⚠ **Printing fees** for monographs and other books are NOT eligible.

Repository requirements (source: Annotated GA HE):

Beneficiaries must ensure deposition of and OA to publications (and research data, where the case) through trusted repositories. For Trees4Adapt, the trusted repository is the [Trees4Adapt Zenodo community](#).

'Repositories' are online archives, where researchers can deposit digital research outputs and provide (open) access to them. Repositories help manage and provide access to scientific outputs and contribute to the long-term preservation of digital assets. They can be institutional, operating with the purpose to collect, disseminate and preserve digital research outputs of individual research organisations (institutional repositories, e.g. the repository of University X) or domain-specific, operating to support specific research communities and supported/endorsed by them (e.g. Europe PMC for life sciences). There are also general-purpose preprint repositories, such as e.g., developed by CERN, BioRxiv (<https://www.biorxiv.org>) or OSF (<https://osf.io>).

Personal websites and databases, publisher websites, as well as cloud storage services (Dropbox, Google Drive, etc.) are **NOT considered repositories**. Academia.edu, ResearchGate and similar platforms do not allow OA under the terms required and therefore are also **NOT considered repositories**.

For more information on OA, please consult GA Article 17 - Annexe 5 (Communication, Dissemination, Open Science and Visibility), in particular the Annotated Model GA provisions and also D1.3 Report on Guidelines on Implementation of the Open Science Practices.

Licensing requirements and IPR:

Scientific publications must be licensed under the latest available version of a Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY 4.0) or an equivalent licence. For

monographs and other long-text formats, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (as in CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND or CC BY-NC-ND or equivalent licences).

For more guidance, including an explanatory checklist of the rights conferred by the above licences that will help researchers to understand publisher-equivalent licences, see the HE Programme Guide.

Beneficiaries (or authors, where the case may be) must retain sufficient IPR to be able to comply with their OA requirements.

 The obligation to ensure open access under the conditions set out in the Grant Agreement precedes any subsequent publishing agreement and is therefore a prior obligation with respect to such agreements.

Best practice: Beneficiaries/authors retain the copyright on their work and grant, insofar as possible, non-exclusive licences to publishers. To facilitate this, beneficiaries should put in place institutional policies to ensure copyright retention by authors and/or beneficiaries and compliance with the open access requirements.

To help you find publishing venues that comply with HE OA requirements, you can use:

- [Journal Checker Tool](#) (Check which publishing options are supported by your funder's OA policy): can help to determine whether a specific publishing venue allows compliance with the OA obligations of HE.
- [Directory of Open Access Journals \(DOAJ\)](#): can help to identify full OA journals that allow OA publishing under CC BY or an equivalent licence.

[Open Research Europe](#): OA publishing platform of the EC, allows automatic compliance with the HE requirements.

4.2.5. Visibility of funding

Project participants are obligated to use the EU emblem when publishing and/or presenting work carried out under the **Trees4Adapt project** (GA Article 17.2). Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must display the EU emblem. This includes conferences, seminars, information material (such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc.), including electronic form via social media and any infrastructure, equipment or major result funded by the grant. **When displayed in association with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.** For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the project participants may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Agency. This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the project must include the following EU emblem and funding acknowledgement:

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme, Grant Agreement No. 101213184 (Trees4Adapt). Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The EU funding emblems and acknowledgements are available on the [Trees4Adapt Teams Folders](#). If you have any queries about their use, please contact ERINN (mathilde@erinn.eu).

4.3. General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) implications

The [GDPR \(EU 2016/679\)](#) provides enhanced protection to individuals' data privacy rights. Organisations storing or using personal data (anything that allows identification of an individual) must clearly disclose what data is being collected and how, why it is being processed/used, how long it is being retained, and if it is being shared with any third parties. Personal data can be names, email addresses, job titles, phone numbers, and anything that allows the identification of an individual.

4.3.1. GDPR compliance (website, mailing list and events)

The [Trees4Adapt project website](#), managed by ERINN, is fully compliant with GDPR by incorporating a Privacy Statement and Cookie Bar informing website visitors about what **Trees4Adapt** does with any personal data gathered. A "Subscribe to News" button is clearly visible on the Homepage, allowing people to voluntarily sign up for the **Trees4Adapt** mailing list. The sign-up page is linked to the Privacy Statement, and subscription is on a double opt-in basis, whereby people who sign up need to confirm their email address to complete the subscription process, ensuring compliance regarding consent under GDPR. The subscription system sends an automatic **Trees4Adapt** email to the subscriber, who then needs to click on the link in the email sent to them. The mailing list is only being used to share **Trees4Adapt**-related information and news. Photographs and videos taken at **Trees4Adapt** project events, workshops, meetings, and promotional activities will comply with the GDPR through the use of consent forms to be signed by all persons involved when relevant. Personal data collected at events will be stored in secure databases and will not be used/shared for any other purpose. Further details on how personal data are handled within **Trees4Adapt**, including storage, access and processing procedures, are described in full in the **Trees4Adapt DMP** (D6.2, M6).

5. Pre- and Post-Dissemination Requirements

5.1. Pre-dissemination requirements

5.1.1. When These Procedures Apply

For all types of publications, dissemination and communication activities (including posters, oral presentations, abstracts, non-scientific materials, etc.) **where:**

1. You plan to share **new Trees4Adapt results or outputs**, and
2. The activity **could expose results that need protection or affect other partners' Intellectual Property (IP)**²,

The procedures also apply to **all scientific publications** resulting from the project.

The [Prior Notice Procedure](#) and the [IP Assessment](#) (respectively Section 1 and 3 of the [Trees4Adapt Prior Notice Form](#)) must be completed **at least 30 calendar days** before the intended date of dissemination.

Partners intending to write a [scientific publication](#) using **Trees4Adapt data, models, or other project outputs** must also complete the **additional** Paper Proposal section (Section 2 of the [Trees4Adapt Prior Notice Form](#)) at least **30 calendar days** before the intended submission of the manuscript.

5.1.2. Prior Notice Procedure

The **main participant** involved in the dissemination of results from the **Trees4Adapt** project (owned by one or several parties) must give the other project participants **at least 30 calendar days**, together with sufficient information on the results they will disseminate (CA section 8.4), by filling out the [Trees4Adapt Prior Notice Form](#).

Any objection to the planned submission or publication shall be made per the Grant Agreement by written notice to the coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination **within 15 calendar days** after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the dissemination is permitted.

PROTOCOL – Prior Notice Procedure

- *Participant(s) proposing a dissemination activity (**submission / publication / poster / presentation**) should inform all project participants of their intent, **at least 30 calendar days** before submitting/publishing, by filling out and submitting the **Trees4Adapt Prior Notice Form**: [Trees4Adapt Prior Notice Form](#).*
- ***Filling out the form will automatically send a prior notice email to the consortium with a calculated 15 calendar-day deadline to object.***

²Intellectual Properties are results that qualify for legal protection (e.g. by copyright, database right, patent, design right, trade secret, or trademark). Not all results qualify; the IP check helps identify which ones could and should be protected before irreversible public disclosure.

- **Sufficient information about the planned dissemination** must be provided within the form in the “summary/abstract” question in Section 1, for partners to determine if their work is affected by the dissemination. If you wish/need to share **additional materials** (e.g., data, draft slides, poster, abstract document, or manuscript) as part of your planned dissemination, please upload them in the Trees4Adapt Teams channel under:

Pre- and Post-Dissemination → **Pre-dissemination** → **Planned dissemination**. Create a folder named: **Date_Institution_Type of Dissemination** and place all relevant files there.

- Project participants have **15 calendar days to object** to the dissemination, if they can show that their legitimate interests in relation to the submission / communication / publication would be significantly harmed if the disclosure is permitted.
- Any objection to the planned submission/publication/dissemination activity shall be made in accordance with the GA by written notice to the **Trees4Adapt** Coordinator and to the participant(s) proposing the submission/publication/dissemination activity, within 15 calendar days after receipt of the notice. **Any objection needs to be justified**, and precise suggested modifications given. An objection is justified if:
 - ✓ It adversely affects the protection of the results/background of the objecting party.
 - ✓ Legitimate interests of the objecting party would be significantly harmed.
 - ✓ The proposed publication includes Confidential Information of the objecting Party (CA Article 8.4.2.2).
- If no objection is made within the above-stated timeline, or if objections are addressed and accepted by the objecting participant(s), the submission/publication / dissemination activity is permitted.
- If an objection has been raised, the involved Parties shall discuss how to overcome the justified grounds for the objection on a timely basis (for example, by amendment to the planned dissemination and/or by protecting information before disseminating), and the objecting Party shall not unreasonably continue the opposition if appropriate measures are taken following the discussion.
- The objecting Party can request a publication delay of not more than **60 calendar days** from the time it raises such an objection. After 60 calendar days, the publication is permitted, provided that the objections of the objecting Party have been addressed.
- In exceptional circumstances, where a dissemination activity is planned **unexpectedly** in a **shorter timeframe**, the notice to other project participants must be given **as soon as possible by sending an email to the consortium** with an abstract including title, author(s), project participants involved and details on where it will be submitted//published.

5.1.3. Intellectual Property (IP)³ Assessment

As outlined in the GA (Annex 5 and Part B, section 2.2), partners must adequately protect their results. An IP check is, therefore, implemented as part of the Prior Notice process, whereby participants who intend to disseminate results are asked to **confirm that there is nothing exploitable and protectable about the results they intend to disseminate**, ensuring no IP is **accidentally exposed** - either their own or that of other partners. Participants must complete section 3 of the [Trees4Adapt Prior Notice Form](#) at least **30 calendar days** before the intended date of dissemination.

Luke will check the information, with support from relevant WP leads and Executive Board members, where needed, as outlined in the protocol below. Partners who are owners of results will ensure that adequate protective steps are taken prior to exploitation. The “Results Ownership List” (ROL) will be included in the final EC report.

PROTOCOL – IP Assessment

- *Filling out section 3 of the Trees4Adapt Prior Notice Form will automatically send an **IP assessment screening** of the intended dissemination activities to Luke (Michael Pashkevich: michael.pashkevich@luke.fi and Katharina Albrich: katharina.albrich@luke.fi) and ERINN (Mathilde Vidal: mathilde@erinn.eu), to ensure protection of results.*
- *This information needs to be received by Luke **at least 30 calendar days** in advance of the intended dissemination activity. Luke will then assess the information, with support from relevant WP leads where needed.*
- ***The Luke team** reviews and communicates with the proposing participant(s) in case of necessary clarifications. The assessment consists of:*
 - a) ***Preliminary screening**, i.e., checking if all information required from the participant is included in section 3 of the Trees4Adapt Prior Notice.*
 - b) ***Reviewing of the activity** (at least the abstract, but ideally the whole publication draft or similar) to identify potentially exploitable knowledge.*
 - c) ***Identification of potential conflicts of interest** related to ownership, authorship and institutions involved, including entities or other projects.*
- *If any information is lacking or insufficient, Luke may request further details from the proposing participant(s) and the assessment period is suspended until the participant responds with adequate clarification.*

³Intellectual Properties are results that qualify for legal protection (e.g. by copyright, database right, patent, design right, trade secret, or trademark). Not all results qualify; the IP check helps identify which ones could and should be protected before irreversible public disclosure.

- *If Luke indicates that the result(s) could (potentially) be considered commercially exploitable, then the participant must carry out their best effort to protect and exploit the result, and the planned activities should be postponed:*
 - a. *In this case, Luke will inform the proposing participant(s) about this situation and request that the relevant participant(s) (together with their technological transfer/IP legal officer(s)), confirm whether these results indeed are commercially exploitable and indicate whether there is an interest in exploiting such results, and how they want to proceed (each participant institution will have a disclosure of invention system).*
 - b. *If it is deemed that the result is commercially exploitable, and if no IP exploitation is envisaged by the owner(s) of the results, it is best practice to consider offering to transfer it to other project participants or third parties better positioned for the exploitation of the results and willing to seek their protection (making sure to comply with granting authority rights GA Annexe 5). In such a case, the project participants or third parties must accept, by written consent to all project participants within **15 days**, to protect the results.*
 - c. *If such a transfer is not done, project participants who have received EU funding but do not intend to protect their results must inform the **EC Desk officer of Trees4Adapt** before any dissemination activity is carried out, through the **Trees4Adapt coordinator team**, who has direct contact with the EC Project Officer. This notification is mandatory for up to four years after the end of the project.*
 - d. *If the owner(s) of the results, other project participants or third parties do not assume the ownership and do not take the necessary measures to protect it, Luke's assessment should be completed within the recommendations of **the IP Assessment Evaluation page** ([Appendix Annexe 1](#)). The recommendations must then be signed by Luke (Michael Pashkevich: michael.pashkevich@luke.fi; Katharina Albrich: katharina.albrich@luke.fi; and Jacqueline Moustakas-Verho, jacqueline.moustakas-verho@luke.fi) and sent to the proposing participant(s), with ERINN (Mathilde Vidal, mathilde@erinn.eu) in copy.*
- *If the intended dissemination or communication activity involving **Trees4Adapt** results does not involve exploitable results, Luke's assessment is complete once the **IP Assessment Evaluation page** is signed by Luke and the Main author of the dissemination.*
- *If there is any doubt on whether the result(s) could (potentially) be considered commercially exploitable, Luke should share the summary of the Trees4Adapt Prior Notice Form and the recommendations of the IP Assessment Evaluation page with the **Executive Board** and ask them to support the assessment (following the steps above).*
- *If no exploitable information is identified, all documents (including the signed IP Assessment Evaluation page) are stored in the Trees4Adapt Teams channel under:*

Pre- and Post-Dissemination → **Pre-dissemination** → **Planned dissemination**. In the appropriate folder. Luke is responsible for informing the proposing participant(s) that they can go ahead with the intended dissemination activity as planned.

5.1.4. Scientific Publication Guidelines

Trees4Adapt is a collaborative research project that combines field measurements, modelling, long-term research platforms such as [TreeDivNet](#), [FunDivEUROPE](#) and [AgroforstMonitoring](#), and contributions from many disciplines. Because data and results are often shared across Tasks and institutions, publications can involve multiple partners and depend on datasets or model outputs generated by others. For this reason, the project follows common rules on documentation, quality, data sharing, and publication procedures. These guidelines support those rules and complement the Consortium Agreement (particularly Section 8). They remain valid throughout the project and until all resulting publications are completed.

All partners intending to write a scientific paper using **Trees4Adapt** data, models, or other project outputs will be asked to complete an extra section (section 2 – Paper Proposal) on the [Trees4Adapt Prior Notice Form](#), **at least 30 calendar days before the intended submission date** of the manuscript.

These guidelines explain how to share information about planned scientific publications arising from **Trees4Adapt**. The aim is to ensure transparency, allow partners to understand what is planned, and identify potential gaps in the methodology, models, data, results, conclusions and authorship early.

PROTOCOL – Only for Scientific Publications

- Filling out **section 2 (Paper Proposal)** of the [Trees4Adapt Prior Notice Form](#) will automatically send the required information on the planned scientific publication to Luke (Michael Pashkevich: michael.pashkevich@luke.fi and Katharina Albrich: katharina.albrich@luke.fi) and ERINN (Mathilde Vidal: mathilde@erinn.eu).
- This information must be received by Luke at least **30 calendar days** before the intended submission date of the manuscript. While Section 1 fulfils the obligations of Prior Notice as stipulated in the Consortium Agreement, **it is encouraged that manuscript ideas be circulated from early stages of development** to give other Trees4Adapt researchers opportunities to contribute. This not only helps to avoid potential bad feelings (e.g., people feeling they were left out of manuscripts) but also can enhance the overall quality and scope of manuscripts owing to collaborative research effort.
- The Paper Proposal section requires the minimum information needed to understand the planned publication, including: preliminary title, identified authors, objectives, datasets and models to be used, methods, expected results, collaboration opportunities, anticipated submission date, and timeline for sharing a first draft with co-authors.

- *The manuscript (and later the submitted version) must be stored in the designated Teams folder (**Pre- and Post-Dissemination** → **Pre-dissemination** → **Planned dissemination**). Create a folder named **Date_Institution_Type of Dissemination** and upload all relevant files there.*
- *Once received, Luke will review the Paper Proposal information provided. If clarifications are required, Luke will contact the proposing author(s).*
- *At least **15 calendar days** before submission, Luke will share the full draft manuscript with the relevant Executive Board members, who will distribute it within their teams where appropriate. The Executive Board review is multi-purpose. It enables a technical check of the manuscript, is an opportunity for Executive Board members to identify potential Key Exploitable Results (KERs) resulting from individual manuscripts ahead of their publication and keep up-to-date with research emerging from the project, and provides a final check to ensure that no other mistakes were made prior to submission (e.g., if a researcher should have been included as co-author).*
- ***When using data or code generated by other Trees4Adapt partners, the following applies:***
 - a) *All data, model outputs, and code must have been deposited in the central [Zenodo Trees4Adapt community](#), with complete metadata and quality checks performed.*
 - b) *If you wish to use data or code from another partner, you must submit a written request to Luke, describing the planned use. Approval from the data/code owner and the relevant Task Leader is required before use.*
 - c) *Only quality-checked and final versions of datasets or code should be used; informal or unreviewed versions should not be exchanged directly. Note that updates to data, including code deposited on the [Zenodo Trees4Adapt community](#), are possible. Such version control is highly encouraged to ensure efficient and high-quality project implementation.*
- ***Timely publication** is important. Rapid dissemination supports early-career researchers, strengthens future funding opportunities, and increases the impact of project results. Since Trees4Adapt is a collaborative project, many manuscripts will involve multiple partners and longer author lists. Access to data needed for collaborative synthesis should not be delayed or restricted, provided authorship and acknowledgement rules are respected.*
- *All Trees4Adapt datasets, model outputs, and code must include complete metadata, see **Trees4Adapt DMP** (D6.2, M6) for full information. If a designated contact person leaves their institution, they must arrange a **complete transfer** of all related data, preliminary results, and documentation to their institution, the coordinating team (Luke: Michael Pashkevich: michael.pashkevich@luke.fi and Katharina Albrich: katharina.albrich@luke.fi) and the relevant WP Lead to avoid loss of project material.*

- *Modelling activities that use Trees4Adapt data must be communicated in advance, especially when the data originates from another participant. All code, model outputs, and methods (including scripts, model names, and input datasets) must be **made available to partners and documented properly in metadata, as described in the Trees4Adapt DMP (D6.2, M6 - March 2026)**. These materials must be deposited in the [Zenodo Trees4Adapt community](#), after quality checks, by the relevant Task Leader and by the coordinating team (Luke: Michael Pashkevich: michael.pashkevich@luke.fi and Katharina Albrich: katharina.albrich@luke.fi). Deposition should normally occur within six months of completing field sampling or laboratory analysis.*
- *Anyone wishing to use data or code produced by another partner, and which is not already openly available, must submit a written request to the relevant Task Leader and/or owner of the data/code, and written approval must be obtained before use. Only quality-checked datasets or scripts should be shared or used; direct informal data exchange between partners should be avoided to maintain consistency and quality.*
- *Releasing Trees4Adapt data or code **outside the consortium** requires written permission from both the Coordinator and the Task Leader responsible for the dataset or code. When the release is done via Zenodo, this is satisfied by the check that Luke does on Zenodo before any submitted outputs are published. When contributions from other partners' data or code play an important role in a manuscript, authorship or appropriate acknowledgement should be discussed early during manuscript preparation to ensure fair credit.*
- ***Authorship should reflect a genuine contribution to the work.** When unpublished data or code from other partners contribute substantially to the main findings, co-authorship is normally appropriate. Acknowledgement or "pers. communication" is appropriate for minor contributions. The data or code owner decides the form of credit. Co-authors must be contacted/informed early to ensure their genuine contribution to the manuscript. Trees4Adapt recommends use of the [Nature Portfolio authorship guidelines](#), which stipulate that authors of scientific publication are expected to have at least 1) made substantial contribution to the manuscript's conception/design OR 2) the acquisition/analysis/interpretation of data OR 3) the creation of new software used in the work OR 4) drafted the work or heavily revised it AND 5) approved the submitted version AND 6) be accountable and ensure the validity of the work.*
- *Researchers or site managers who are involved in essential planning, implementing, coordination, and/or provide infrastructure, or measurement-site support for Trees4Adapt - including WP Leaders and managers of external networks used in the project (e.g., TreeDivNet, FunDivEUROPE, Agroforst-Monitoring sites) - **should be proactively invited to contribute to manuscripts** arising from the relevant Tasks, where they can contribute meaningfully to the manuscript.*
- *Publication policies of external networks associated with Trees4Adapt (e.g. **TreeDivNet, FunDivEUROPE, Agroforst-Monitoring**) must also be respected when their data, sites, or infrastructures are used. These networks have their own rules for data use and authorship, so authors must check the relevant policy and ensure the manuscript complies before submission.*

- *Partners preparing manuscripts should ensure that any data or outputs used in the publication **follow Trees4Adapt data management rules**. Destructive or disturbance-based sampling in the field must always follow agreed written protocols and must be approved by site owners or managers before being carried out. The location, timing, and details of all measurements or sampling activities must be documented in the metadata and deposited together with the corresponding dataset.*
- *All scientific publications arising from Trees4Adapt must include the **required EU funding acknowledgement**:*

“Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme, Grant Agreement No. 101213184 (Trees4Adapt). Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

5.2. Post-dissemination requirements

As part of the EU contractual requirements, all **Scientific Publications**, **Dissemination Activities** and **Communication Activities** are reported as part of the **Continuous Reporting** of the project in the EC Funding and Tender Opportunities Portal (EC Portal).

5.2.1. Continuous Reporting of Scientific Publications

NOTE: Scientific Publications resulting from Trees4Adapt are collated and uploaded to the EC Portal by ERINN. Project participants **DO NOT** need to upload this information to the Portal themselves. Participants are encouraged to send their publications to ERINN (mathilde@erinn.eu) and Luke (Michael Pashkevich: michael.pashkevich@luke.fi; Katharina Albrich: katharina.albrich@luke.fi, and Jacqueline Moustakas-Verho: jacqueline.moustakas-verho@luke.fi) as soon as available and **no later than two weeks after the official publication date**. At the same time, participants are asked to add it to the Scientific Publication continuous log located on the [Trees4Adapt Teams Folders \(Pre- and Post-Dissemination channel\) / Post-dissemination / Continuous Logs – tracking / Scientific publications log](#), see detailed Protocol in [PDEC section 3.2.2](#) below and ([Appendix Annexe 2](#)).

Scientific Publications must be uploaded to the EC Portal by ERINN once they have been accepted for publication. This includes articles in journals, publications in conference proceedings/workshops, books/monographs, chapters in a book, theses/dissertations, etc.

5.2.2. Continuous Reporting of Dissemination and Communication Activities

NOTE: All Dissemination Activities and Communication Activities of Trees4Adapt are collated and uploaded to the EC Portal by ERINN. Project participants **DO NOT** need to upload this information to the EC Portal themselves. To successfully manage the recording of

these activities, ERINN requires all participants to routinely update the dedicated **Trees4Adapt** continuous Reporting Logs for Dissemination Activities and Communication Activities which are shared as live documents with all participants and located on [Trees4Adapt Teams Folders](#) ([Pre- and Post-Dissemination channel](#) / [Post-dissemination](#) / [Continuous Logs – tracking](#) / [Communication activities](#) or [Dissemination activities](#) log) ([Appendix Annexe 2](#)).

PROTOCOL – EC Reporting of Scientific Publications, Dissemination Activities and Communication Activities

1. **All project participants** are required to keep track of all their Scientific Publications, Dissemination Activities and Communication Activities during project implementation.
2. The three **Trees4Adapt** Continuous Reporting Logs ([Publications](#), [Dissemination](#) and [Communication](#)) have been developed by ERINN to support the reporting of these activities ([Appendix Annexe 2](#)). The Continuous Reporting Logs have been shared with all project participants and can be found in the [Trees4Adapt Teams Folders](#) (under the [Pre- and Post-Dissemination channel](#)/[Post-dissemination](#)/[Continuous Logs – tracking](#) folder).
3. Project participants should regularly contribute information to update the different Logs to report on 1) Scientific Publications, 2) Dissemination Activities and 3) Communication Activities.
4. The logs will be reviewed by ERINN for completeness and correctness at the EC reporting stages, and validated information will be updated in the EC portal by ERINN.
5. Peer-reviewed publications, communication and dissemination materials (example: conference presentation or poster, etc) must be uploaded on the [Trees4Adapt Zenodo community](#) in their final version.

5.2.3. Patents (IPR) reporting

Trees4Adapt participants are responsible for tracking their IPR resulting from the project. Whenever a new IPR has been filed (the EC recommends filing with the European Patent Office), participants are required to notify the coordinators (Michael Pashkevich: michael.pashkevich@luke.fi; Katharina Albrich: katharina.albrich@luke.fi, and Jacqueline Moustakas-Verho: jacqueline.moustakas-verho@luke.fi) and ERINN (Mathilde Vidal, mathilde@erinn.eu) with the relevant information. Luke will share the completed IP Assessment Evaluation page ([Appendix Annexe 1](#)) with the Executive Board ([see PDEC section 5.1.3](#)). Project participants are responsible for uploading the required information about their IPR directly to the EC Portal.

Participants are required to provide the following details:

- Identification of IPR Type and Confidentiality
- Type of IPR (Patent/Trademark/Registered Design/Utility Model/Other)
- Confidentiality (Yes/No)
- Application Title

5.2.4. Datasets

Trees4Adapt participants are responsible for recording and uploading all datasets resulting from the project to the EC Portal and the [Trees4Adapt Zenodo community](#). For further details on the project and HE-specific rules for data outputs, please see **Trees4Adapt DMP** (D6.2 due in M6 - March 2026).

5.2.5. Overview of Post-Dissemination Continuous Reporting Protocols

Item	Action needed by the acting participant	Participant uploading to EC Portal
Scientific Publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Record Scientific Publications in the Trees4Adapt Continuous Reporting Publication Log Add publication to the Trees4Adapt Zenodo community 	ERINN
Dissemination Activities and Communication Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Record all Dissemination activities and Communication activities in the corresponding Trees4Adapt Continuous Reporting Logs Add final material to the Trees4Adapt Zenodo community 	ERINN
Patents (IPR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Record and upload the required information Notify Luke and ERINN of the new IPR filed 	Participant owning the IPR
Datasets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Record and upload all datasets Add datasets to the Trees4Adapt Zenodo community Notify Luke 	Participant owning the dataset(s) ⁴

For guidance on how to complete other sections of the continuous reporting in the EC portal (e.g. Researchers involved in the project, Deliverables, Milestones, Results, Standards, Impact), please refer to the [Trees4Adapt Project Manual](#) (D6.1 delivered in M3 - Dec 2025).

6. Stakeholder engagement

The purpose of the stakeholder engagement activities described in the **Trees4Adapt** PDEC is to support continuous dialogue, build trusted relationships, and enable meaningful exchanges and co-creation between the project and the societal users of its outputs. Early and sustained stakeholder involvement ensures that Trees4Adapt's research remains grounded in real-world needs and insights and maximises the project's potential to influence policy, practice, and risk-related decision-making across Europe.

⁴ In case of joint datasets, or even IPR, only one participant is required to upload to the EC portal.

Stakeholder engagement in **Trees4Adapt** is coordinated within **WP5 (Stakeholder engagement, dissemination, exploitation and communication)**, led by **Prospex Institute (PI)**, which applies structured and professional methods, including the **Stakeholder Integrated Research (STIR) approach** and the **Prospex-CQI method**, to identify, select, and engage relevant actors at local, regional, national, and EU levels ([see PDEC section 6.3 below](#)). WP5 activities include stakeholder mapping across governance levels, facilitating co-creation in the case studies (diversifying Finland's Forests; agroforestry in German farmlands; post-fire recovery in Portugal), organising bilateral consultations, establishing an online platform for continuous exchange, and delivering validation and testing workshops to guide the development of exploitable outputs. Engagement will involve public authorities, forest and land managers, farmers, local communities, policymakers, the wider scientific community, and other relevant users of the project's results.

In parallel, **dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities**, also integrated into WP5, support stakeholder engagement in raising awareness, promoting knowledge exchange, and strengthening the relevance and uptake of project results. **Communication and Dissemination** efforts led by **ERINN (T5.5)** ensure that stakeholders, policymakers, and the wider public remain informed about **Trees4Adapt's** aims, activities, and achievements. **Exploitation** planning led by **Luke (T5.6)** will build on insights gained through engagement activities to co-develop a **post-project exploitation strategy (D5.8, due M46 - July 2029)** with IPR owners and key stakeholders. **All project partners** contribute to these integrated activities to ensure that the project's solutions are usable, accepted, and positioned for long-term impact.

6.1. Internal stakeholders - project bodies

6.1.1. The General Assembly (GeA)

The **General Assembly (GeA)** is the **decision-making body** of the **Trees4Adapt** consortium. It consists of one representative from each beneficiary organisation (multiple representatives of organisations may attend GeA meetings, but there is always one vote per beneficiary) and meets at least once per year. The GeA is responsible for overseeing the overall direction and governance of the project, including decisions related to project activities (e.g. proposed changes to the work plan or background issues), finances (e.g. budget reallocations), intellectual property rights (IPR), and consortium composition (e.g. admission or withdrawal of partners, defaulting parties, project termination, or change of Coordinator). It also serves as the final authority for resolving disputes that cannot be settled by the Executive Board.

The members of the GeA are:

Participant	General Assembly members
1. Luke	Michael Pashkevich, Katharina Albrich, Jacqueline Moustakas-Verho
2. UGent	Pieter de Frenne
3. Uni Würzburg	Sarah Redlich

4. IIASA	Martin Jung
5.PI	Yulia Poskakukhina, Katharina Faradsch
6. FMI	Juha Aalto
7. UFR	Michael Scherer-Lorenzen
8. RHUL	Julia Koricheva
9. IGOT	António Monteiro
10. ISA	Susana Barreiro
11. ERINN	Mathilde Vidal
12. UTU	Kai Ruohomäki

Each organisation has one vote in the GeA, regardless of the number of people listed/present.

6.1.2. The Executive Board (EB)

The **Executive Board (EB)** is **responsible for the day-to-day management and operational coordination** of the **Trees4Adapt** project. It consists of the Coordinators, the Administrative Manager, the Work Package Leaders, and any additional members appointed by the General Assembly. The EB meets at least quarterly, either in person or online, including during Consortium Meetings.

The EB oversees the implementation of project activities and the decisions of the General Assembly, monitors progress and effectiveness, and identifies and addresses risks and ethical issues. It organises General Assembly meetings, proposes agendas, and collects and analyses project progress information every six months. The EB reviews compliance with the work plan, recommends adjustments where needed, and resolves disputes that cannot be settled at the WP or task level. It is also responsible for ensuring compliance with ethical, social, and environmental standards, including privacy, data protection, non-discrimination, and the protection of human health and the environment.

The EB plays a key role in project monitoring and quality assurance. Progress indicators are established at the project start together with the Stakeholder Board, and the EB works with the Coordinators to monitor progress across all WPs. All deliverables undergo internal peer review assigned by the EB, and the EB reviews all resulting outputs. WP Leaders submit six-monthly progress reports to the EB, and partners report financial progress to the Coordinators for consolidation. Gender balance in project activities and events is also monitored and reported to the EB every nine months, following internal reporting.

Regarding IPR and exploitation, **the EB supports the protection of project results by assessing emerging outputs and their potential need for protective measures**. The EB helps Luke ensure that IPR considerations remain coherent with the GA and CA and that appropriate protection is in place before dissemination or communication occurs ([see PDEC section 5.1.3](#)).

The members of the EB are:

Participant	General Assembly member	Role	WP
Luke	Michael Pashkevich	Coordinator (Chair)	WP6
Luke	Katharina Albrich	Coordinator	WP6
Luke	Jacqueline Moustakas-Verho	Administrative Manager	WP6
UGent	Pieter de Frenne	Work Package Leader	WP1
Uni Wuerzburg	Sarah Redlich	Work Package Leader	WP2
Luke	Aino Assmuth	Work Package Leader	WP3
IIASA	Martin Jung	Work Package Leader	WP4
PI	Yulia Poskakukhina	Work Package Leader	WP5
8. ERINN	Mathilde Vidal	Project Communications	WP5

6.1.3. The Stakeholder Board (SB)

The **Stakeholder Board (SB)** provides independent, practice-grounded advice and strategic input to **Trees4Adapt**. Comprising approximately 6-8 external stakeholders from relevant decision and policymaking bodies and communities of practice (e.g., public authorities and policymakers, researchers, tree-based solution (TbS) practitioners, landowners and managers such as farmers and foresters), the SB is appointed and steered by the General Assembly (GeA).

The SB assists and facilitates GeA decision-making by offering feedback on research and innovation activities and on the usability and uptake of project outputs. Members may be invited to Consortium Meetings and, upon invitation, to GeA meetings in an advisory capacity without voting rights. The Coordinator ensures that a non-disclosure agreement is executed with each SB member/organisation, prepares minutes of SB meetings, and submits them to the GeA.

The current members of the SB will be displayed in the next PDEC version (D5.5 - PDEC 2nd update, M18 - Mar 2027), to ensure that none of them object to having their names publicly displayed.

6.1.4. The Case Study (CS) leaders

The **CS leaders**, or co-leaders, coordinate their local CS activities. They are responsible for ensuring that participants carry out the planned tasks and contribute to high-quality deliverables. CS leaders also foster collaboration among partners within their CS, as well as across other case studies and relevant project tasks.

The CS leaders are:

Location	Participant	CS leader(s)
Finland	RHUL	Julia Koricheva
Germany	Uni Wuerzburg	Sarah Redlich

Portugal	ISA	Susana Barreiro
	IGOT	António Monteiro

6.2. Stakeholder engagement strategy

Trees4Adapt's stakeholder engagement strategy ensures that the project's research and outputs are informed by the needs, perspectives, and experiences of the people who will use or be affected by them. Engagement is integrated throughout the project and coordinated under WP5 by PI, with activities at local, regional, national, and EU levels. The aim is to support the co-creation of relevant and usable solutions, improve the uptake of project results, and strengthen the long-term impact of **Trees4Adapt**.

At the local level, WP5 supports the three CS in mapping local and other stakeholders, developing co-creation plans, and engaging communities, public authorities, land managers, and others. **At the regional, national, and EU levels**, WP5 will apply structured identification and engagement processes to involve key users of the project's envisaged outputs, including policy tools, decision support products, and practical solutions.

WP5 will **build on the strong existing networks** of PI and other partners, including collaborations with public authorities, forestry and agriculture actors, environmental NGOs, and EU-level bodies such as DG ENV, DG CLIMA, Forest Europe, and IUCN. **Trees4Adapt** will create synergies with other large EU-funded climate and biodiversity projects and with the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change activities, helping to broaden engagement while reducing duplication and stakeholder fatigue.

6.2.1. STIR approach

WP5 will use the **Stakeholder Integrated Research (STIR) approach**⁵. STIR is a structured and professional approach for the identification and engagement of stakeholders in climate change and land use science. STIR ensures that stakeholders actively participate in all phases of the project by interacting with the research goals and scientific information developed in the project and offering their guidance and feedback, which in turn is integrated into the project implementation. The method has been/is being successfully applied in a wider range of other large Horizon EU projects. STIR includes five key features:

- **Stakeholder evaluation and compatible scientific set-up**: ensuring that research questions and plans align with stakeholder needs.
- **Participatory integration of stakeholders in the research process**: involving stakeholders directly in co-creation and decision-making.
- **Prospex-CQI method for stakeholder identification and selection**: a transparent and representative approach for selecting participants at different governance levels ([see PDEC section 6.2.2 below](#)).

⁵ Gramberger, M., Zellmer, K., Kok, K., & Metzger, M. J. (2015). Stakeholder integrated research (STIR): a new approach tested in climate change adaptation research. *Climatic Change*, 128(3-4), 201-214. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-014-1225-x>

- **Design and facilitation of the stakeholder engagement process:** using professional moderation, structured workshops, and formats such as policy labs and bilateral consultations.
- **Methods for stakeholder–science data transfer:** ensuring that information flows clearly between researchers and stakeholders and informs decision-making.

Fig 1. Features of the Stakeholder Integrated Research approach (Gramberger et al., 2015)

6.2.2. Prospex-CQI method

Trees4Adapt will use **the Prospex-CQI method (part of the STIR approach)** to identify and select relevant stakeholders at the local, regional, national, and EU levels. This method ensures that participation is representative, diverse, and aligned with the project's needs. It applies a three-step structure:

- **Criteria (C):** defining a set of criteria and categories (e.g., stakeholder groups such as policymakers, forest managers, farmers, etc.) or stakeholder groups that are affecting the research topic, being affected by it, or both.
- **Quotas (Q):** setting minimum representation to ensure demographic balance and diversity, including gender.
- **Individuals (I):** identifying specific people who meet the criteria and are well-positioned to provide input.

The method ensures transparency, reduces selection bias, and strengthens the legitimacy and usability of the project's outputs.

Across the levels, stakeholder mapping in **Trees4Adapt** will build on the suggested end-user groups of the estimated project's key exploitable results (KER) as identified below.

6.3. Trees4Adapt-specific stakeholder activities

Trees4Adapt's stakeholder engagement activities are organised across three main levels: **local case study engagement** (T5.2), **regional/national/EU engagement** around the project's exploitable outputs (T5.3), and **EU-level legacy and policy engagement** (T5.4). These activities complement each other and supply continuous input to research WPs, communication activities, and the exploitation strategy. The following sections summarise each of these engagement layers.

6.3.1. Local-level engagement

At the local level, WP5 **supports the three case studies** in expanding their networks, mapping relevant local actors, and developing and implementing their case study co-creation strategy and plan (D5.2, due M10 – July 2026). In each CS, this document will outline the targeted strategy and actions for the meaningful involvement of a diverse range of actors, including public authorities, land managers, farmers, community organisations, and other stakeholders. The strategies/plans and WP5 will guide the preparation and implementation of the co-creation workshops in the CS, which support the co-design and testing of optimised tree-based solutions, and gather input on local challenges, needs, and expectations. The insights generated through these activities will contribute directly to the development of best-practice manuals and case-specific recommendations and ensure that the solutions proposed by the project reflect local conditions and priorities. These efforts will be reported in D5.9 (due M46 - July 2029), which will document the outcomes of the local-level co-creation processes and engagement across the three case studies.

Building on existing stakeholder networks, each CS aims to identify additional relevant actors and strengthen stakeholder diversity by mapping groups and individuals who haven't been engaged or identified as relevant stakeholders so far. The resulting extended stakeholder networks will support inclusive co-creation processes and provide a basis for sustained stakeholder engagement across the three CS. While within each CS, the primary focus will be on local stakeholders and regional ones, the CS teams are also encouraged to identify stakeholders at the national level and beyond, both to promote their work and local perspectives at the national scale and to support potential future upscaling.

The CS have started their stakeholder mapping immediately after the discussion between CS leads and PI at the start of the project. This initial stakeholder-mapping phase will continue through the first months of 2026, ahead of and after the first co-creation workshop in each CS in February and March 2026, to further refine and expand the stakeholder base and to ensure balanced representation across relevant categories and sectors.

PI did a stakeholder mapping exercise as part of **Milestone 2** (M3 - December 2025), where CS teams, supported by WP2 partner IGOT-UL, identified initial groups, organisations, and individuals relevant to their local contexts. This mapping established the first version of the CS-specific stakeholder networks. A summary of the mapped stakeholder groups is available in Milestone 2, which provides an overview of the actors considered most relevant at this early stage. Further details on stakeholder categories, engagement needs and roles will be presented in D5.2 (Case Study Co-creation Strategies and Plans, due M10 – July 2026). Additional information on the first co-creation workshops and subsequent engagement

activities will be included in the next PDEC update (D5.5, M18 – March 2027), once these activities have taken place.

It is important to note that stakeholder mapping is an iterative process that will continue throughout the project duration.

Insights from case study engagement

At the project kick-off meeting in Finland in November 2025, PI facilitated three internal visioning exercises focused on the three CS.

For each CS, in three groups representatives of the three CS and other partners (who chose which group to join) worked through four structured steps: 1) articulating a vision for the situation they would like to see at the end of the project thanks to their work (e.g., policymakers are making informed decisions on forest management directed at maximising biodiversity restoration, climate change mitigation and other societal benefits); 2) identifying the sequential actions required to progress towards it; 3) determining which stakeholders would need to be involved at different stages; and 4) defining the value proposition that would make engagement meaningful for those actors. The purpose of this exercise was to establish a shared internal understanding of each CS's ambitions and to lay the groundwork for more formal stakeholder mapping and engagement activities that will take place throughout WP2. The exercise is a method commonly used by PI as a first step in helping partners and external actors develop their stakeholder engagement strategy.

Fig 2. Figure 1: Visioning flipchart layout

Fig 3. Visioning posters from all 3 case studies (left: Portugal case study: Serra de Estrela; middle: Finnish case study: Satakunta tree-diversity experiment; right: German case study: Agroforestry in German farmlands)

Fig 4. Digitalised versions of the three visioning exercise flip-charts (left: Portugal case study: Serra de Estrela; middle: Finnish case study: Satakunta tree-diversity experiment; right: German case study: Agroforestry in German farmlands)

6.3.2. Regional, national and EU-level engagement

Engagement at regional, national, and EU levels focuses on the intended users of **Trees4Adapt's** policy recommendations, decision-support tools, models, and maps. This strand of engagement will begin with stakeholder mapping (MS4, due M10 - July 2026) and will continue through a series of structured activities, including bilateral consultations with key stakeholders, a validation workshop (MS14, due M30 - March 2028), and three online test-run workshops (MS20, due M42 - March 2029). In addition, an **online stakeholder engagement platform** will be established and linked to the [Trees4Adapt website](#), where stakeholders will be able to find relevant information and register. This will allow partners and stakeholders to connect and communicate, encouraging direct knowledge exchange across regions and organisational levels and expansion of the network over time. These activities will allow stakeholders to be informed early about **Trees4Adapt's** planned outputs, to inform the vision for the latter early on with their perspectives and needs, and to assess the usability and relevance of draft tools and recommendations. The feedback collected will help refine and improve the exploitable outputs and ensure they are designed in a way that supports real-world decision-making. The engagement activities carried out under T5.3 will be documented in D5.4 (due M18 - March 2027), D5.6 (due M36 - Sep 2028), and D5.10 (due M46 - July 2029), and will feed directly into the project's exploitation planning under Task 5.6 ([see PDEC section 7 below](#)).

6.3.3. EU-level legacy event

In the final year of the project, PI will organise a **two-day EU-level legacy event in Brussels**, combining the final consortium meeting with a roundtable involving at least 20 EU-level policymakers and stakeholder organisations. This roundtable will present the project's tools, models, maps, and policy recommendations; discuss their implications for EU and national adaptation and biodiversity policies; and explore pathways for mainstreaming and upscaling the project's outputs beyond its lifetime. Representatives of other large EU-funded climate and biodiversity projects will also be invited to ensure alignment and reinforce synergies across initiatives. The event will draw on insights gathered throughout the project's stakeholder engagement activities and will inform the development of the post-project exploitation strategy (D5.8, due M46 - July 2029).

7. Management of results and exploitation

7.1. Expected end-user groups, pathways and impact

The end-user groups presented in this section reflect those expected to benefit from, or make use of, several anticipated **Key Exploitable Results (KERs)**. These KERs were highlighted as particularly relevant to the topic's⁶ expected outcomes and relevant policy frameworks.

These KERs represent the project's current expectations regarding the types of outputs likely to emerge from **Trees4Adapt's** research and engagement activities. Additional exploitable results may develop as the project progresses, and the set of KERs will be refined, expanded, and updated accordingly. This section provides an overview of the currently anticipated KERs (see Table 1), defines the expected end-user groups, and summarises the main engagement pathways and expected impacts associated with each end-user group in support of future exploitation (see Table 2).

⁶ HORIZON-MISS-2024-CLIMA-01-04: Research the complex interplay between the climate and biodiversity crises towards more systemic approaches and solutions.

Table 1. List of expected Key Exploitable Results (KERs).

KER#	Title	Impact	Target audience	Linked WP(s)	Linked Deliverables
KER1	Publicly available field-quantified datasets for studying how CC and BL interdependently affect whole ecosystems.	Datasets will enable researchers to assess and model CC and BL more effectively, closing knowledge gaps.	Researchers	WP1, WP2	D1.1-5; D2.2-3
KER2	Evaluation of the relative benefits and trade-offs of individual tree species and mixtures for climate adaptation and biodiversity conservation.	Evaluations will provide species- and mixture-specific recommendations for improving future TbS implementation that involves tree planting.	Researchers, forest and farm managers, tree planting campaigns, and TbS practitioners	WP1, WP2	D1.1-5; D2.2-4
KER3	Co-created best-practice manuals on designing and implementing TbS.	Manuals will recommend strategies for more-effective TbS design and implementation, including ways to avoid maladaptation and how TbS address specific risks. All WPs contribute.	TbS practitioners, landowners and managers, authorities and policymakers, local business owners, insurance providers	WP2	D2.4
KER4	Novel bioeconomic models, validated on CS data, that indicate the economic costs and benefits of TbS.	Models will assist decision-makers in prioritising investments towards TbS that cost-effectively reduce risk from CC and BL.	Researchers, authorities, policymakers, investors, and TbS practitioners	WP2, WP3	D3.2.
KER5	High-resolution maps describing current and future complex risks to	Maps will enable more precise assessments of complex risks from CC, BL, and their interdependencies.	Authorities and policymakers, land use planners, researchers	WP4	D4.1-3.

	biodiversity and water systems.				
KER6	Decision support tool to enable strategic decision-making towards climate resilience and biodiversity conservation and restoration.	The interactive online tool will improve understanding of region-specific risks across the EU and where authorities should prioritise TbS implementation for long-term benefits. All WPs contribute.	Authorities and policymakers, land use planners, TbS practitioners, researchers	WP4	D4.3.
KER7	Policy briefs recommending actions that should be prioritised to address CC and BL	Briefs will distil Trees4Adapt's nuanced research findings into concrete recommended changes in policy and practice.	Authorities & policymakers, land managers, TbS practitioners	WP1, WP5	Informed by deliverables: D1.1-D4.3 and delivered via D2.4/D4.4.
KER8	Network of stakeholders from the local to EU-levels who are committed to addressing CC and BL, including beyond Trees4Adapt's lifetime.	In addition to in-person and online workshops, an online platform on Trees4Adapt's website will allow partners and stakeholders to connect and communicate, encouraging direct knowledge exchange across regions and organisational levels and expansion of the network over time.	Authorities and policymakers, land use planners, forest and farm managers, TbS practitioners, researchers	WP5	D5.2, D5.4, D5.6, D5.9, and D5.10

❖ Industry and practice

This group includes forest and land managers, farmers, agroforestry practitioners, TbS practitioners, forest owners, landowners, consulting organisations involved in land-use planning, and local business owners affected by climate and biodiversity risks. These users are central for KER2 (species-level recommendations), KER3 (best-practice manuals for TbS), and KER6 (decision-support tool). Insurance providers, investors, and actors assessing risk mitigation or long-term adaptation benefits are also relevant here, particularly in relation to KER4 (bioeconomic models) and KER6 (decision-support tools).

❖ Public authorities, policymakers, and regulators

European, national, regional, and local authorities responsible for land management, biodiversity conservation, climate adaptation, rural development, and environmental regulation are core users of multiple KERs. This includes DG ENV, DG CLIMA, the JRC, Member State ministries, regional planning authorities, and local administrations. Policymakers are particularly targeted for KER3 (best-practice manuals), KER5 (risk maps), KER6 (decision-support tool), and KER7 (policy briefs). **Trees4Adapt** also aims to reach decision-makers involved in investment prioritisation for adaptation measures, TbS implementation, and risk governance.

❖ Scientific community

Researchers and academic institutions working on climate change, biodiversity loss, ecosystem functioning, land-use change, ecological modelling, nature-based solutions, and risk assessment are key users of several Trees4Adapt KERs. This includes communities specialising in high-resolution modelling, bioeconomic modelling, biodiversity and water risk mapping, and contributors to major science-policy platforms such as the IPCC and IPBES. KER1 (datasets), KER2 (species evaluations), KER4 (bioeconomic models), and KER5 (risk maps) all directly support research needs and are designed to close knowledge gaps and enable more robust modelling and assessment.

❖ Civil society, NGOs, communities

Environmental NGOs, community groups, restoration networks, and citizen-focused organisations play a role in promoting resilient land-use practices, TbS implementation, and awareness of climate-biodiversity interactions. These users benefit from the practical recommendations in KER3 (best-practice manuals) and the insights summarised in KER7 (policy briefs). They also contribute to and engage with the wider stakeholder network described in KER8.

❖ Related EU projects, initiatives

Trees4Adapt will work with and contribute to synergies with other EU-funded projects and knowledge platforms, including major NbS, climate adaptation, biodiversity, and risk assessment initiatives. Relevant groups include Trees4Adapt's sister project TerraTwin, ForestPaths, SafeNet, COEVOLVERS, SPARCCL, ACCREU, CLIMAAX, MYRIAD-EU, Mission "Adaptation to Climate Change" current projects, Climate-ADAPT, CORDIS, the Horizon Results Platform, NetworkNature+, and other EC and international bodies such as the

EEA, IPCC, IPBES, and the JRC's Risk Data Hub. These actors support the uptake, visibility, and integration of Trees4Adapt findings within wider European research and policy agendas and are directly linked to KER8 (stakeholder network).

❖ Trees4Adapt stakeholder network

KER8 focuses specifically on developing a sustained network of stakeholders across local, regional, national, and EU levels, ensuring ongoing dialogue beyond the project's lifetime. This network includes authorities and policymakers, land-use planners, forest and farm managers, TbS practitioners, and researchers. Through a combination of in-person workshops, online consultations, and an online exchange platform, this group supports the co-development, testing, and long-term adoption of **Trees4Adapt** results.

Table 2. Trees4Adapt stakeholder engagement strategy.

End user groups	Tools of engagement	Expected impact
Industry <i>(forest and land managers, farmers and agriculture stakeholders, TbS practitioners, forest owners, etc.)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder Board members • Co-creation activities in the CS (workshops, testing of TbS, best-practice development; T5.2) • Existing and new partner links with relevant European and international organisations, associations, innovation clusters, groups and agencies • Bilateral consultations on exploitable outputs (T5.3) • Validation workshop (M30) and test-run workshops (M36–42) • Best-practice manuals (KER3) and species-level recommendations (KER2) • Decision-support tool (KER6) • Communication channels: website, social media, articles, videos, infographics (T5.5) • Public deliverables: CS reports, bioeconomic models (KER4), risk maps (KER5) • OA publications in sector-specific & industry relevant magazines • Online exchange platform? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased understanding of how TbS can support climate adaptation, biodiversity, and long-term land productivity • Improved decision-making capacity for selecting resilient species mixtures, TbS designs, and management options • Enhanced ability to reduce climate-related economic losses using cost-benefit insights from bioeconomic models (KER4) • Greater confidence in adopting science-based, context-specific TbS informed by co-creation with stakeholders
Scientific community <i>(researchers in ecology, forestry, climate science, land-use change, modelling, biodiversity, risk assessments, etc.)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open-access datasets, publications (including in the emerging field of CC-BL integrated science) and code repositories (Trees4Adapt Zenodo Community) • Presentations at scientific conferences and workshops • Public deliverables from WP1–4 (species evaluations, models, maps) • Online exchange platform (KER8) • Facilitation of knowledge transfer between researchers and practitioners via STIR Feature • Project website, press releases, news articles • Social media (LinkedIn, Bluesky) campaigns 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved capability to assess and model the impacts of climate and biodiversity crises in an integrated way • Greater access to high-quality datasets, models, and tools supporting interdisciplinary research • Strengthened scientific community around CC-BL interactions and TbS design • Enhanced contributions to global science-policy platforms (IPCC, IPBES)

<p>Policy & regulation</p> <p><i>(EU, national, regional, and local authorities; DG ENV, DG CLIMA, JRC; land-use planners; public administrations)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bilateral consultations (≥20 by M20) • Validation workshop with 15–20 policymakers (M30) • Test-run workshops (≥3, M36–42) • Policy briefs (KER7) • Decision-support tool and high-resolution risk maps (KER5, KER6) • Best-practice manuals (KER3) • EU-level roundtable during final legacy event (T5.4) • Collaboration through stakeholder networks and platforms • Public deliverables from WP1–4 (species evaluations, models, maps) • Participation & presentation of the project results at high-level conferences/advisory bodies • Policy briefs for regional, national, and EU levels. Focused on CC, BL, and interdependencies • Online exchange platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evidence-based tools enabling prioritisation of climate adaptation and biodiversity actions • Better identification of high-risk areas and investment priorities at local and regional levels • Improved policy alignment with the EU Green Deal, Forest Strategy, Climate Adaptation Strategy, CAP, and the Nature Restoration Law • Strengthened inter-regional cooperation via “homologous regions” identified through KER6
<p>Society</p> <p><i>(NGOs, environmental organisations, communities, citizen groups, restoration networks, educators)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public website, press releases, articles (T5.5) • Social media campaigns targeting awareness of CC–BL interactions • Accessible communication materials (videos, animations, infographics) • Project branding & promotional materials (factsheet, banners) • Engagement with relevant activists & influencers • Engagement through case study activities, community workshops, and local exchanges • Best-practice manuals and policy briefs in accessible formats • Public outreach activities (<i>e.g. participation in European Researchers’ Night, partners’ open days, International Day of Forests events, EU Green Week, and other forest-related awareness initiatives</i>) • <i>Online exchange platform – for the bigger NGOs, at least</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased public understanding of climate-biodiversity interdependencies and the role of TbS • Greater acceptance of evidence-based management and restoration actions • Empowerment of local communities to engage in adaptation, restoration, and sustainable land-use decisions • Stronger support for EU climate and biodiversity policy goals

<p>Related EU projects, initiatives & networks</p> <p><i>(TerraTwin, ForestPaths, SUPERB, COEVOLVERS, SPARCCE, CLIMAAX, ACCREU, MYRIADEU)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public deliverables from WP1–4 (species evaluations, models, maps) • Active collaboration & coordinated communication & dissemination activities with relevant projects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ exchange of R&D results & good practices ◦ knowledge-sharing webinars ◦ joint stakeholder workshops & events ◦ joint sessions at conferences ◦ joint publications, and policy recommendations • Collaboration with the sister project funded under the same call: TerraTwin (started Jan 2026) & projects funded within the Horizon Europe missions “Adaptation to climate change” and EU projects creating mitigation pathways for forest-use in Europe (e.g., SafeNet, CLIMAAX, Pathways2Resilience, WildCard, etc.) • Collaborate with ongoing initiatives (e.g., CLIMAAX, MYRIAD-EU, ACCREU, SPARCCE, Copernicus for Atmosphere and Climate Change, Biodiversa+, etc.) • Joint events with EU projects from other calls • Project website, press releases, news articles • Social media (LinkedIn, Bluesky) campaigns 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stronger synergies and reduced duplication between EU-funded projects • Contributions to harmonised EU risk assessments and science-policy dialogues • Increased opportunities for coordinated research and joint activities & better use of resources (optimising synergies & avoiding overlaps), helping to optimise synergies and avoid duplication • Enhanced project visibility and legacy, through integration into European research infrastructures and alignment with ongoing initiatives in forest and biodiversity monitoring • Enhanced contribution to EU policy development, through the integration of Trees4Adapt outputs into broader science-policy dialogues and platforms
<p>Cross-cutting stakeholder network.</p> <p><i>(public authorities, land-use planners, forest & farm managers, TbS practitioners, researchers across Europe)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An active multi-level stakeholder network built through WP5 • Online exchange platform hosted on the Trees4Adapt website • Continuous engagement via consultations, workshops, and co-creation activities • Final EU-level roundtable and ongoing networking opportunities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A durable, pan-European network supporting long-term collaboration after the project (KER 8) • Continued uptake and refinement of Trees4Adapt outputs beyond the project’s lifetime • Sustained contribution to EU Mission Adaptation objectives and climate-resilient transformation

7.2. Exploitation management approach

Exploitation in **Trees4Adapt** is integrated within WP5 and is coordinated under Task 5.6, led by Luke. The approach focuses on ensuring that project outputs which have clear potential for post-project use are identified, shaped with users, protected where appropriate, and supported with realistic pathways for uptake and scaling. Exploitation is iterative and evidence-led: it draws on the continuous stakeholder input generated by engagement activities (T5.2–T5.4) and on partner communication efforts (T5.5), while remaining consistent with the principles and procedures set out in the GA and CA. The EB supports this process by reviewing emerging results, including their exploitation potential, and advising on IPR considerations before any public disclosure. Result owners are responsible for implementing appropriate protective steps ahead of exploitation, dissemination, or communication.

7.2.1. Output identification and collection

Confirmation and identification of new potential **KERs** (see **Table 1**) is a continuous process that begins with collecting all project outputs. Processes regarding output management are outlined in the D6.2 DMP (due M6 – March 2026) and, briefly, include depositing outputs on the [Trees4Adapt Zenodo community](#). Once uploaded, the lead researcher for each output and the EB members can jointly determine the output's exploitability and therefore whether it qualifies as a KER. Research WPs must provide concise descriptions of emerging outputs, including their intended users, maturity, and dependencies. Partners will contribute and will be reminded to report their outputs continuously within Trees4Adapt's continuous reporting process and through insights gathered during bilateral stakeholder meetings, case study activities, and thematic workshops. This rolling process ensures that expected outputs (e.g., datasets, models, maps, decision-support tools, best-practice manuals, policy briefs) and unanticipated results are captured, assessed, and tracked for exploitation planning.

7.2.2. Co-creation, testing, and refinement of outputs

Trees4Adapt will develop its outputs through iterative co-creation with intended users, followed by structured validation and test-run cycles to ensure usability, relevance, and real-world applicability. Co-creation within the project effectively began with the first CS workshops, where partners and local actors started working together to identify needs, constraints, and context dependencies and to shape early design choices for tools, maps, models, best-practice guidance and policy recommendations. These activities are building on pre-existing stakeholder relationships held by some partners, where relevant, while also engaging new stakeholders who had not previously been involved. This formative stage includes practical interactions, such as field-based exchanges and facilitated workshops, that help translate emerging evidence into user-centred project outputs and case-specific guidance.

As project outputs develop, PI will run targeted consultations with regional, national, and EU-level users to help shape their direction, identify early-stage gaps, and prioritise features

and needs (structured engagement; T5.3). These consultations support the initial design and refinement of outputs before they reach a mature stage. Once draft concepts and prototypes are available, a validation workshop will be organised to review these mid-stage versions with representative users, gather feedback on clarity, usefulness, and potential barriers, and guide further improvements. Later, when the outputs reach a near-final stage, a series of test-run sessions will be held in which stakeholders trial the almost-ready versions, provide detailed usability input, and confirm application settings and data requirements. The insights from these steps will feed directly into the final refinement of content, functionality, formats, and accompanying documentation to support uptake.

In the final stage, **Trees4Adapt** will convene an EU-level roundtable to position the **refined outputs** within policy and implementation pathways, discuss mainstreaming and upscaling options, and identify interfaces with relevant European platforms and initiatives (legacy and policy engagement; T5.4). Throughout these cycles, partners will document decisions and rationales so that improvements are traceable and reproducible, and -where relevant- the EB will review emerging results and advise on intellectual property protection before any public disclosure.

7.2.3. Roles and responsibilities

Luke will lead the development of the post-project exploitation strategy, drawing together input from engagement activities, partner contributions, and the wider stakeholder network, and ensuring that the proposed exploitation routes reflect user needs and relevant policy contexts. **PI** will provide and facilitate targeted inputs from its stakeholder engagement activities, including insights generated through stakeholder mapping, co-creation processes, and validation exercises, which will help ensure that the proposed pathways are grounded in a clear understanding of user expectations, barriers, and enablers. **Luke**, with the support of the EB, will provide oversight by reviewing emerging results, assessing their exploitation potential, and providing guidance on intellectual property considerations in line with the GA, the CA, and Horizon Europe principles. A **final project event** will also form part of the project's exploitation approach. **PI** will lead its organisation and will work closely with **Luke** to ensure that the event aligns with and supports the post-project exploitation strategy.

All project partners will contribute to exploitation by identifying potential exploitable results within their work, applying appropriate protection measures before disclosure, providing input to validation and test-run activities, and supporting the development of realistic and actionable pathways for uptake after the project's end.

8. Dissemination and communication resources and activities

8.1. Promotional materials

8.1.1. Logo and brand

A specific project logo has been developed to visually represent the project. The project logo is an integral part of the brand, as it is and will be included in all the project's promotional materials, both print and online. The **Trees4Adapt** project logo with tagline, a version of the logo without tagline and the separated tree mark are available in three different versions: a full colour and a black and white version. The different versions and guidance on how to properly utilise the **Trees4Adapt** logo (correct use of the logo about the background, spacing, etc.) can be found in the Brand Guidelines that have been developed alongside the logo.

The Logo Suite and Brand Guidelines are available on the [Trees4Adapt website](#) in the Promotional Material page, on the [Trees4Adapt Teams Channel in the Branding material folders](#) and can be requested from ERINN (mathilde@erinn.eu).

Fig 5. Trees4Adapt logo with tagline (full colour)

PROTOCOL – Utilising Trees4Adapt branding alongside other institutional branding

While it is preferable that all participants use **Trees4Adapt**-branded resources when disseminating the project's results, we recognise that some institutions will require participants to use their own institutional branding for conferences and various presentations. To balance

the interests of **Trees4Adapt** and our contractual obligations to the EC, with various institutional requirements, we require the following to be included at a minimum:

- The **Trees4Adapt** logo must be included on at least the title page and conclusion/thank you slide; however, usage on all slides would be preferred.
- The EU emblem and funding acknowledgement (GA Article 17) must be visibly present on the first and last slide.

8.1.2. Project dissemination templates

Trees4Adapt PowerPoint and Poster Presentation Templates, Word Report and Deliverable Templates have been developed to use at internal and external events when presenting the **Trees4Adapt** project and/or its outcomes and can be downloaded from the [Trees4Adapt Teams Channel in the Branding material folders](#) or requested from ERINN (mathilde@erinn.eu).

PROTOCOL – Dissemination Templates

Project participants should use the **Trees4Adapt** dissemination template documents when promoting the project's objectives or presenting project results.

The template can be downloaded from the [Trees4Adapt Teams Channel in the Branding material folders](#) and/or requested from ERINN (mathilde@erinn.eu).

- When using the PowerPoint presentation template, choose to insert “new slide” and pick your preferred content template.
- Respect all of the templates' format (background, font and layout).
- Always ensure that the correct EU Emblem, EU funding logo and acknowledgements are present on any **Trees4Adapt** dissemination (*e.g., presentations, deliverables and reports, etc*).

8.1.3. Factsheet

A promotional factsheet (double-sided A4 format) presenting the **Trees4Adapt** objectives and expected results will be developed within the Portfolio of Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) material to promote and outreach (D5.3, due M12 – September 2026). The factsheet will be shared digitally and distributed at relevant events, both virtually and in person. The factsheet will be used to raise awareness of the project and its goals. It will be found on the [Trees4Adapt website](#), on the [Trees4Adapt Teams Channel in the Branding material folders](#), and it will be possible to request it from ERINN (mathilde@erinn.eu). Project participants will be encouraged to distribute the factsheet through their networks and at

relevant events. If participants ever wish to have the factsheet available in another language, they should follow the protocol outlined below.

PROTOCOL – Factsheet translation

- Contact ERINN (mathilde@erinn.eu) requesting the original factsheet template with English text.
- ERINN supplies the template with the original text in English to the requesting project participant.
- The project participant translates the text (as laid out in the template) into their language.
- The project participant then sends a translated text back to ERINN.
- ERINN applies the translated text to the factsheet template and publishes the new version of the factsheet, after validation and sign-off from the project participant responsible for the translation.

8.1.4. Infographics

A number of infographics will be developed to support communication about **Trees4Adapt's** structure, objectives, and activities. Initial materials will include an infographic on the interactions between **Trees4Adapt's** work packages and a map of partner countries and activities' locations, which partners may use in presentations, posters, and general outreach. Additional infographics will be produced during the project to explain specific aspects of **Trees4Adapt's** work or to support dissemination around key outputs, depending on needs identified by partners or through stakeholder engagement. Infographics will be part of the Portfolio of Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) material (D5.3, due M12 – September 2026) and will be made available on the [Trees4Adapt Teams Channel in the Branding material folders](#). Partners may request further formats or language versions from ERINN (mathilde@erinn.eu), if needed.

8.1.5. Website

The **Trees4Adapt project website** [trees4adapt.eu] went live in M6 (March 2026). The full website has been (and will continue to be) developed in line with the EU's best practice guidelines for project websites. The website is also fully compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (EU 2016/679, GDPR) by incorporating a privacy statement and cookie bar informing website visitors about what **Trees4Adapt** does with any personal data gathered. Google Analytics is used to track traffic and monitor the use of the website, which will be used to inform **Trees4Adapt's Continuous Reporting**.

To ensure the successful promotion of the project and to sustain the interest of the target audience and attract new users, the website's content will be maintained, continuously updated and populated with new information throughout the project's lifetime. The website will

remain live for five years after the end of the project, serving as a valuable public resource of research information on the subject and promoting the outputs of this publicly funded research.

Key features of the website include:

- **About section:** introduction to the Trees4Adapt project, including the project team, being part of the EU Mission Adaptation to Climate Change and the overview of the project's challenge, objectives and expected impact.
- **Project Activities section:** explanation of the work planned in the different work packages with an interactive map.
- **Case studies section:** introduction to the three case studies with image gallery.
- **News & Events section:** regular updates featuring project news, upcoming events organised by the **Trees4Adapt** consortium, and relevant content from related initiatives and topics of interest to website visitors and **Trees4Adapt** stakeholders.
- **Results & Resources section:** latest scientific papers, policy briefs, reports and public deliverables from the project, as well as latest resources/promotional material that have been produced to promote **Trees4Adapt**, including printed media, digital media, audio and videos.
- **Project Team sub-section:** introduction to the **Trees4Adapt** consortium, as well as the executive board members. The current members of the stakeholder boards members will be displayed in the website after we ensure that none of them object to having their names publicly displayed.
- **Related Links section:** introduction to the related projects, initiatives and networks, including links to their website and social media channels.
- **Subscribe to News button:** allow website visitors to subscribe to project news by filling out a form.

The stakeholder engagement online exchange platform will be created by PI by M20 – March 2027 and will be linked to the Trees4Adapt project website in a dedicated page, which will contain more information on how to register.

PROTOCOL – Website content: requests for posting and uploading

- ERINN manages the **Trees4Adapt** website and will be updating it on a regular basis.
- Any project participants who have feedback about the website should contact ERINN (mathilde@erinn.eu).
- All partners are encouraged to regularly send materials, photos, news and/or events to ERINN (mathilde@erinn.eu) to upload on the website.

- All partners are requested to include a link to the **Trees4Adapt** website on their own institution's websites as well as promote it through their channels ([see PDEC section 8.1.6 below](#)).

8.1.6. Social media

Social networking is an integral part of the **Trees4Adapt** communication strategy. The project results and outputs will be actively disseminated through the project LinkedIn ([@Trees4Adapt Project](#)), Bluesky ([@trees4adapt.bsky.social](#)) and Instagram ([@Trees4Adapt](#)) accounts managed by ERINN. Stakeholders are encouraged to follow **Trees4Adapt**'s social media, which serve as forums for engagement with interested parties and contribute to capacity building, showcasing participant expertise and knowledge through active discussions.

At M6 (March 2026), the statistics of **Trees4Adapt**'s social media presence are:

	Bluesky	LinkedIn	Instagram
Creation date	(M1) 01/11/2025	(M1) 01/11/2025	(M1) 18/11/2025
Followers	79	192	43
Number of posts	24	55	6
Total number of impressions	1,132	5,225	267

As with all communication channels, it is important to carefully consider the content shared on social media. The consortium should decide which information remains private and which can be published, including where and to what extent. If you are unsure about what is appropriate, please contact ERINN (mathilde@erinn.eu).

To maintain **Trees4Adapt**'s reputation and foster an engaging, thriving online community, it is essential to manage potential risks effectively. The following guidelines apply to all participants using social media, whether posting on **Trees4Adapt**'s official accounts, their personal or organisation accounts, or engaging with content on other platforms.

PROTOCOL – Trees4Adapt's internal code of social media conduct

Participants should try to contribute to social media channels where possible. Support can be requested from ERINN.

General Rules

- Ensure the content is yours to share (research or opinions) or acknowledge the source accordingly.
- Ensure there are no IP issues.

- Use appropriate tags and hashtags to acknowledge EU funding (see below for platform-specific examples).
- Do not use offensive language, argumentative or illegal content, *etc.*
- If you communicate publicly about **Trees4Adapt** or **Trees4Adapt-related** matters, you must disclose your role within the project.
- Maintain a professional tone, exercise good judgment, and ensure your communications are accurate and honest. Inappropriate language or behaviour can damage the project's reputation and may lead to legal consequences.
- Unless approved by the coordinator (Luke), your personal social media name, handle, and URL should not include the **Trees4Adapt** project's name or logo.
- Be considerate when discussing sensitive or potentially controversial topics, such as politics. Always show respect for differing opinions and maintain a respectful tone.

Platform-Specific Guidelines: LinkedIn, Bluesky and Instagram

Participants are encouraged to help increase **Trees4Adapt's** visibility and engagement in LinkedIn ([@Trees4Adapt Project](#)), Bluesky ([@trees4adapt.bsky.social](#)) and Instagram ([@Trees4Adapt](#)) by following these practices:

- If you would like content shared from the official **Trees4Adapt** accounts, please email your message to ERINN at (mathilde@erinn.eu). For Bluesky, keep messages under 300 characters. Whenever possible, include an image or short video to enhance visual appeal.
- When posting from your personal or institutional accounts, tag **Trees4Adapt** using the appropriate handle ([@Trees4Adapt Project](#) on LinkedIn, [@trees4adapt.bsky.social](#) on Bluesky and [@Trees4Adapt](#) on Instagram). ERINN will repost or share tagged content.
- Repost or share updates from the **Trees4Adapt** posts through your own LinkedIn and Bluesky profiles to help broaden the project's reach.

Tips

- Social media is increasingly visual, so include images, videos, GIFs or data visualisations to make your posts more engaging.
- Interact with your audience through replies, shares and tags and ask questions rather than making statements to encourage conversation.
- Make use of existing networks by tagging and following relevant accounts such as your host institution, research team members or partner organisations. When posting, always tag the project ([@Trees4Adapt Project](#) on LinkedIn, [@trees4adapt.bsky.social](#) on Bluesky and [@Trees4Adapt](#) on Instagram). If space allows, also tag relevant EU bodies, on LinkedIn: @ Mission Implementation Platform for Adaptation to Climate Change (MIP4Adapt),

@European Research Executive Agency (REA), @European Commission or @EU Environment and Climate; on Bluesky: @mip4adapt.bsky.social, @ec.europa.eu, @euclimateaction.bsky.social or @horizoneu.bsky.social; on Instagram: @agroforst_monitoring, @zoo3wuerzburg, @theglobalgoals, @climate.connect.global, etc.

- Add relevant hashtags such as: #Trees4Adapt #TreeBiodiversity #TreeBasedSolutions #NatureBasedSolutions #HorizonEurope #EUFundedProject.
- Share content such as project milestones, results, scientific publications, press releases or participation in conferences and events.

8.1.7. Project videos

A **visual storytelling video** will be developed to support the communication and promotion of the **Trees4Adapt** project at events and on social media. It will aim to introduce the project to a broad audience, focusing on the challenge it addresses, the project's objectives, and the expected results and impact. The video will showcase the project to the general public, explaining the approach and the value of the work being conducted by **Trees4Adapt's** partners. More videos and clips will be produced later in the project to showcase results and further promote **Trees4Adapt's** impact.

The videos will be promoted on the [Trees4Adapt website](#) and social media channels. Project participants will be encouraged to share them through their own networks and upload them to video-sharing platforms such as YouTube and Vimeo to help extend the project's reach.

8.1.8. Press releases and promotional articles

Press releases are distributed to relevant media outlets, including trade publications, journals and web portals, to raise awareness of the project, its objectives and its outcomes among industry, communities, civil society, policymakers and the broader public. This approach is designed to generate media coverage at local, regional, European and international levels.

ERINN will share project news through both internal channels (such as the internal consortium email list and participant networks) and external ones (including press releases, promotional articles, project news subscribing page and social media channels), ensuring wide visibility and awareness of the project across relevant stakeholders. Project participants are encouraged to publish articles and press releases at regional, national, and international levels, using their own communication networks and platforms. ERINN is available to support participants in these efforts.

8.1.9. Other resources and tools

As the project progresses, a range of high-quality outreach materials will be developed to communicate **Trees4Adapt**'s activities and findings in an engaging and accessible way. These may include more infographics, articles and case study summaries to highlight project results, and other media designed to support communication campaigns across European media and through the channels of project partners and relevant stakeholders.

All resources and tools will be made available on the [Trees4Adapt website](#) under the Promotional Material section, and project participants will be encouraged to share them through their own networks. Additional promotional materials may be developed depending on budget availability and sustainability considerations. For suggestions or support with communication materials, please contact ERINN (mathilde@erinn.eu).

8.2. Activities

The purpose of **Trees4Adapt**'s dissemination and communication activities is to raise awareness of the project, its results and its activities among the wider public. These efforts aim to ensure that stakeholders beyond the immediate project community can understand and engage with its messages. All **Trees4Adapt** participants are expected to contribute time to dissemination and communication and are encouraged to foster a two-way exchange with the public and, where possible, the media. The goal is to highlight the positive impact of EU research and innovation funding on society. Through these activities, **Trees4Adapt** will also demonstrate the value of European collaboration in addressing challenges that affect communities across Europe and beyond.

8.2.1. PDEC tools, channels and audiences

A key element of the **Trees4Adapt** dissemination and communication strategy is the co-development of messages and materials through ongoing engagement with key stakeholders. As the project advances, it will be essential to ensure that outcomes are effectively transferred to relevant users in policy, industry, research and local communities. Tailored strategies will be applied for each target audience, using appropriate messaging, channels and language. To promote the project concept and results and support the achievement of expected impacts, a range of communication tools and activities has been designed (**Table 3**). These are being implemented by the consortium and coordinated and monitored by WP5.

Table 3. Tools, channels and audiences for communicating **Trees4Adapt**'s work and measuring impact.

Communication and Dissemination tools & channels to increase Trees4Adapt 's visibility and showcase work, sharing regular news and result updates to reach out and communicate to target audiences, raising awareness about the project and triggering engagement with project outputs.	Industry	Scientist	Policy	Society
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<p>Project website & online communication platform:</p> <p>Main communication tool as it provides easy access to a broad audience around the world. The website is being designed following the best practice guidelines for EU project websites. The platform facilitates interactions between partners & stakeholders.</p> <p>Target: online at M06 and for at least 5 years after project end. Regular updates. > 7,000 visits over the project duration, > 100 signed up to the mailing list through the website.</p>	✓	✓	✓	✓
<p>Branding portfolio:</p> <p>Presentation templates, infographics, and factsheet: presented & distributed at relevant events & online by all partners.</p> <p>Target: >5,000 people over the project duration.</p>	✓	✓	✓	✓
<p>Press releases & promotional articles:</p> <p>Produced regularly, making use of a range of services & publications aimed at increasing awareness about the project's objectives, progress & outcomes.</p> <p>Target: ≥10 original press releases or promotional articles published, leading to further publication of at least 20 articles in websites, the press, and specialised publications.</p>	✓	✓	✓	✓
<p>Videos:</p> <p>Introduce the challenge, the project & its objectives, as well as project outcomes & contributions.</p> <p>Target: ≥1 professional video & ≥5 shorter media clips viewed by >10,000 people over the project duration.</p>	✓	✓	✓	✓
<p>Social media strategy:</p> <p>LinkedIn, Bluesky and Instagram are engaging general audiences and targeted stakeholders. Project participants amplify content via their own social media, highlighting relevance to their audiences and directing traffic to Trees4Adapt channels and website. Metrics are measured using analytics functions provided within the social media platforms used.</p> <p>Target: social media presence at latest from M3 (December 2025), with LinkedIn, BlueSky and/or other relevant social media activity and targeted promotional campaigns (for promoting specific topics) reaching >50,000 people over the full project duration.</p>	✓	✓	✓	✓

<p>Participation in relevant external virtual & physical events:</p> <p>Trees4Adapt will be represented at major relevant international (research, policy & industry) events over the full duration of the project.</p> <p>Target: Trees4Adapt will be represented in multiple relevant international events (e.g., the International Conference on Forests for Biodiversity and Climate, ESA Living Planet Symposium, UNEP, and International Union of Forest Research Organisations events).</p>	☑	☑	☑	
<p>Project network and events:</p> <p>Trees4Adapt will foster synergies, increase visibility, and enhance impact through cooperation with related Horizon Europe projects and initiatives, contributing to shared goals and mutual learning.</p> <p>Target: Trees4Adapt will have an active cooperation with other relevant projects funded by Horizon Europe, such as CLIMAAX, MYRIAD-EU, ACCREU, SPARCCLE and projects funded under “Mission Adaptation to Climate Change” (esp. HORIZON-MISS-2024-CLIMA-01-04 sister project: TerraTwin and HORIZON-MISS-2024-CLIMA-01-09 projects: COAST-SCAPES, SMARTER and SystR) and/or other relevant EU projects/initiatives (e.g., Copernicus for Atmosphere and Climate Change, Biodiversa+), including the JRC’s Risk Data Hub. Events by DG-CLIMA, DG-ENV & EIP-AGRI.</p>	☑	☑	☑	☑
<p>Open Access (OA) scientific publications:</p> <p>Trees4Adapt will publish its research in high-impact peer-reviewed journals, review articles, & editorials articles.</p> <p>Target: 20 OA publications over the full project duration, of which at least four (one per WP1-4) will be considered core contributions to their fields and the emerging field of CC-BL integrated science.</p>		☑	☑	
<p>Policy briefs:</p> <p>Trees4Adapt will develop evidence-based policy briefs focused on CC, BL, and interdependencies, how these influence risk, and how TbS can address complex risks; spatial explicit implementation of TbS; and co-creational approaches to TbS design and implementation.</p> <p>Target: design policy briefs at the regional, national, and EU levels.</p>			☑	
<p>Final conference:</p> <p>Trees4Adapt will host a high-level final event near Brussels to present project outcomes, including a presentation of Trees4Adapt’s contribution to the framework for the joint monitoring of biodiversity and climate aspects on forests among key stakeholders & general & specialised media [T5.4].</p>	☑	☑	☑	☑

Target: final event near Brussels with participation from key stakeholders and media, showcasing Trees4Adapt’s policy-relevant contributions.				
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8.2.2. External events

All project participants have a responsibility to engage the public in their research activities, results, and take advantage of the potential for public interest that **Trees4Adapt** is generating. Project participants are encouraged to initiate dissemination activities that are appropriate for their respective contributions, and ERINN can provide support as required. Examples include live webinars, blogs, organisation open days, local outreach days, etc.

The project results are being presented as oral presentations, posters, etc., at major international meetings and conferences of relevance to **Trees4Adapt**. Conferences, seminars, workshops and other meetings are very useful forums to consult with **Trees4Adapt's** target audiences in a face-to-face capacity and to address issues relevant to the work done in the project. International and sector-relevant conferences, meetings, etc., will be frequently attended to communicate the results of the project to the maximum number of persons. See the protocol for public outreach activities below.

Table 4 shows a list of past and future events that were already attended or are of interest to **Trees4Adapt** participants or stakeholders in the future. These events are added to the project website on an ongoing basis under the “News & Events” section.

Table 4. Non-exhaustive list of relevant events for the **Trees4Adapt** consortium and stakeholders

Event	Location	Date
ChangeNOW 2026	Paris, France	30 March - 01 April 2026
European Climate Summit (ECS) 2026	Barcelona, Spain	11 - 14 April 2026
Fifth Forum for the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change	Nicosia, Cyprus	27-28 May 2026
Stockholm Ministerial Conference 2026	Stockholm, Sweden	02 - 03 June 2026
GARP 2026 Climate and Nature Risk Symposium	London, UK	09 - 10 June 2026
EFI 2026 Annual Conference	Växjö, Sweden	16 - 18 September 2026
CBC2026 - Connecting Biodiversity, Climate, and Human Behaviour	Leipzig, Germany	21 - 24 September 2026
Nature-based Solutions International Congress 2026	Paris, France	03 - 06 November 2026

COP31 – UN Climate Change Conference	Antalya, Turkey	09 - 20 November 2026
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PROTOCOL – Public outreach activities: internal & external events

- Project participants should **inform ERINN and the project coordinator (Luke) of any planned outreach activities** so they can be promoted. Project participants should notify ERINN if there is news suitable for an official project press release.
- Project participants should notify the full consortium about upcoming outreach activities so that all project participants are aware and can coordinate or support as needed. If the activity involves the dissemination of **Trees4Adapt** results, ensure compliance with the **Trees4Adapt** protocol and complete the **Trees4Adapt Prior Notice Form** ([see PDEC section 5.1](#)).
- Project participants must track and report all outreach activities during internal and external reporting periods. To this end, record all outreach activities, including participation in external events, in the **Trees4Adapt** communication or dissemination **continuous reporting log**, providing insight on the type of activity, objectives, target audiences, and reach (rough estimate of the number of people) ([see PDEC section 5.2](#)).
- ERINN will include events on the **Trees4Adapt** website and promote them through the project’s social media channels and network.

8.2.3. Scientific publications – relevant journals

Trees4Adapt researchers will target high-impact, peer-reviewed, open-access journals across ecology, climate science, biodiversity, forest science, modelling, and sustainability transitions. The selection below includes journals that are well-aligned with the project’s core disciplines, including climate–biodiversity interactions, forest and ecosystem science, spatial modelling, socio-ecological systems, and climate adaptation research, as well as interdisciplinary and policy-oriented outlets for work on tree-based solutions, governance, and co-creation. These journals may be considered depending on the focus of each manuscript.

Potential scientific journals include: *Nature Climate Change*; *Nature Ecology & Evolution*; *Nature Sustainability*; *Global Change Biology*; *Ecology Letters*; *One Earth*; *Biological Conservation*; *Conservation Biology*; *Journal of Applied Ecology*; *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*; *Forest Ecology and Management*; *Landscape Ecology*; *European Journal of Forest Research*; *Ecological Applications*; *Ecography*; *Ecosystems*; *Environmental Research Letters*; *Environmental Science & Policy*; *People and Nature*; *Ecosystems and People*; *Sustainability Science*; *Ambio*; *Climatic Change*; *Environmental Modelling & Software*; *Remote Sensing in Ecology and Conservation*; *Ecological Indicators*; *Restoration Ecology*; *Journal of Environmental Management*; *Ecosystem Services*; *Frontiers in Forests and Global Change*; *PLOS Climate*; *PLOS Biology*; and *PLOS Sustainability and Transformation*.

In the case of potential hybrid journals like *Forest Policy & Economics* and *Land Use Policy*, make sure to have read the Open-Access rules and guidelines from the EC ([see PDEC section 4.2.4](#)). Note that published scientific articles in OA in hybrid journals will count for the project targets, but the publication fees will not be eligible for reimbursement by the EC.

This list will evolve as research outputs mature, and final journal selection will depend on the nature of each manuscript and the target audience.

9. PDEC monitoring and evaluation

The PDEC functions as a living operational manual and will be updated throughout the project to reflect ongoing DEC activities and results. Task 5.1, led by ERINN, is responsible for reviewing and amending the PDEC in line with project developments. **Each version of the PDEC must be validated by the consortium.** Updates are planned regularly as deliverables throughout the project's duration:

- D5.5 - PDEC 2nd update (M18 - Mar 2027)
- D5.7 - PDEC 3rd update (M36 - Sep 2028)
- D5.11 - PDEC final update (M48 - Sep 2029)

In line with the project's evaluation protocol (see the [Trees4Adapt Project Manual](#) D6.1 delivered in M3 - Dec 2025), each deliverable is peer-reviewed by at least two internal experts. For the PDEC, the designated reviewers are the WP5 leader (PI) and the project coordinator (Luke). The review process was conducted in a live document, shared with the full consortium simultaneously. This allowed for transparent, real-time commenting and feedback.

10. Project participants involved in the work

All project participants are expected to carry out dissemination and exploitation activities as well as communication activities. Luke will provide coordination and support for exploitation activities. ERINN will provide support for dissemination and communication activities.

11. Appendix

➤ Annexe 1 – IP Assessment Evaluation Page

IP Assessment Evaluation

Author's information:

Name	
Institution	
Type of dissemination	
Date of intended dissemination	
Title of the proposed dissemination	

Recommendations:

<p>Project coordinator Luke's recommendation:</p> <p>(to publish or protect)</p>	
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Signatures:

Project coordinator Luke	Main author of the dissemination
Date:	Date:
Signature:	Signature:

➤ **Annexe 2 – Trees4Adapt continuous reporting logs**

Note that the first row, in yellow, is an example only and not a real entry for the project.

Communication activities:						
(Events (press conferences, outreach meetings, workshops, internet debates, round tables, group discussions, etc.), Exhibitions, Interviews, Media articles, Newsletters, Websites, Press releases, Print materials (brochures, leaflets, posters, stickers, banners, etc.), Social media, TV/Radio campaigns, Videos, Others)						
Activity name	Target audience Reached Choose between the following options: (Industry, business partners Innovators EU Institutions National authorities Regional authorities Local authorities Civil society Citizens Research communities Specific end user communities International organisation (UN body, OECD, etc.) Investors Other) Can add more than one	How? Communication channel (one choice only) Select the most relevant <i>Event** (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)</i> <i>Print materials** (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)</i>	Description of the activity (max 200 characters) Write a sentence	Outcome (was it well spread?) Mention specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	Date of the communication activity	Partner who wrote this information [name + organisation + WP] - in case more details are needed
Trees4Adapt LinkedIn account (PR1)	Citizens Research communities	Social media	Trees4Adapt LinkedIn communicates about the project by sharing news and related events.	The LinkedIn Trees4Adapt account counts a total of 50 posts and 187 followers, it received 5.2k impressions and reached 3.2k viewers between its creation in November 2025 and February 2026	November 2025 - February 2026	Mathilde Vidal (ERINN) WPS

[To add Dissemination activities please refer to the Dissemination activities log.](#)

Dissemination activities:					
(Scientific conferences, Workshops, Education and training events, Science focus meetings, Clustering activities, Collaboration with EU-funded projects, Other scientific collaborations, Other scientific cooperations, Others)					
Activity name	Type of dissemination activity	Target audience Reached Choose between the following options: (Industry, business partners Innovators EU Institutions National authorities Regional authorities Local authorities Civil society Citizens Research communities Specific end user communities International organisation (UN body, OECD, etc.) Investors Other) Can add more than one	Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output Write a sentence. (max 200 characters)	Dates	Partner who wrote this information [name + organisation + WP] - in case more details are needed
2025 Open Living Lab Days of the European Network of Living Labs (ENOLL) - conference	Conferences	Research communities, Specific end user communities, EU Institutions	ESSRG Presented SafeNet project, focusing on our stakeholder engagement strategy at the ENoLL conference and was awarded Best Innovation Presentation	1 October 2025	Bence Lukács (ESSRG) WP1

[To add Communication activities please refer to the Communication activity log](#)

Publications

Note: Once research has been published, please inform ERINN (contact: mathilde@erinn.eu) and copy Luke (contacts: michael.pashkevich@luke.fi, katharina.albrich@luke.fi and jacqueline.moustakas-verho@luke.fi), so that the publication can be added to the project website.

Type of PID (repository)	Type of publication	PID (publisher version of record)	Title of the scientific publication For a book chapter, write the title of the chapter, not the book	Authors	Date	Journal (or equivalent)	ISSN or eISSN (International Standard Serial Number) Is used for journals, magazines, and other serial publications	Publisher	Was the publication available in open access through the repository at the time of publication?	Peer-reviewed?	PID of Book	Book title	Did you charge OA publishing fees to the project?	Article processing costs (APCs) that will be charged to the project? (€)	Partner(s) involved (Organisation + name + WP)	Link to the publication in the repository (Trees4Adapt Zenodo)
DOI	Article in journal	https://doi.org/10.1002/tra.4265	Environmental DNA time series analysis of a temperate stream reveals distinct seasonal community and functional shifts	Mandy Sander, Arne J. Beermann, Dominik Buchner, Iris Madge Pimentel, James S. Sinclair, Martina Weiss, Peter Haase, Florian Leese	9-Mar-24	River Research and Applications	ISSN 1535-1459	WILEY	Yes	Yes	/	/	Yes	Confidential	Peter Haase (SGN), WP3	https://www.authorea.com/users/602937/articles/633564-environmental-dna-time-series-analysis-of-a-temperate-stream-reveals-distinct-seasonal-community-and-functional-shifts-but-no-influence-of-within-stream-sampling-position

Tree-based Solutions
4 Climate Change **Adaptation**
& Biodiversity Conservation

Project Coordination

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More Information

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Bluesky | [@trees4adapt.bsky.social](https://trees4adapt.bsky.social)

LinkedIn | [@Trees4Adapt Project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/trees4adapt-project)

Instagram | [@trees4adapt](https://www.instagram.com/trees4adapt)

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trees4adapt.eu

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 [@Trees4Adapt Project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/trees4adapt-project)

 [@trees4adapt](https://www.instagram.com/trees4adapt)